

Materials for the e-learning course on how to incorporate Open Science (D4.1)

Research infrastructures cooperation for energy transition between European and Latin American and the Caribbean countries.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the materials developed for the Energytran e-Learning Course on Open Science, “*Environmental challenges and open science – an approach from innovation and technology*”, aimed at training researchers and professionals to apply Open Science principles in energy transition, natural capital, and climate change research.

Developed under WP4 “Mobilities for sustainability”, the course supports European Union (EU) and Latin American and Caribbean (LAC) cooperation, enabling the transfer of knowledge and skills while fostering open, transparent, and reproducible research practices. The course materials translate some of the project’s technical outputs developed under WP5 into practical resources, providing a tangible demonstrator of Open Science in action.

The course is organized into four modules covering global challenges, monitoring and evaluation of science, open scientific knowledge, and participation of social actors. Each module includes presentations, case studies, readings, and self-assessment activities, hosted on a Moodle platform with multilingual support (Spanish and English).

The pilot edition in San José, Costa Rica (22-26 September 2025) validated the materials and structure, with participants reporting high satisfaction (96% rated the course good or very good). Feedback confirmed the relevance, clarity, and usability of the content, as well as the value of the hybrid and multilingual format (simultaneous translation to Spanish, Portuguese and English).

The deliverable demonstrates Energytran’s capacity to produce reusable, scalable training materials that promote Open Science adoption, enhance research capacity, and strengthen EU-LAC collaboration in sustainable energy and environmental research.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Energytran project aims to strengthen scientific cooperation between the EU and LAC by advancing the exchange and co-creation of knowledge on the energy transition. In line with the project’s overarching goal of promoting sustainable and inclusive research systems, Energytran places particular emphasis on the adoption of Open Science principles as a means to foster transparency, collaboration, and innovation across regions.

Open Science represents a transformative approach to research, encouraging the sharing of data, methodologies, and results, and the active participation of diverse social actors in the scientific process. Within the fields of energy and environmental sustainability, Open Science plays a key role in accelerating the transition towards low-carbon systems, enhancing the reusability and accessibility of knowledge, and bridging the gap between science, policy, and society.

Within this framework, the present deliverable documents the development and implementation of the e-learning course “Open Science for the Energy Transition”, designed as part of Work Package 4 “Mobilities for sustainability”. The course provides researchers and professionals with conceptual and practical tools to integrate Open Science practices into their work, with particular relevance to topics such as climate resilience, natural resource management, and sustainable energy systems.

The e-learning programme has been developed as a modular training resource, combining theoretical content with applied examples. It is hosted in a Moodle-based virtual learning environment and supported by a hybrid delivery model that accommodates both in-person and virtual participation.

This deliverable presents:

- The objectives, structure, thematic content and materials of the course;
- The technical implementation of the e-learning platform;
- The pilot experience, including the methodology, participant engagement, and feedback collected through a satisfaction survey.

By developing and validating these e-learning materials, Energytran contributes to its expected impact of promoting cross-regional knowledge exchange and capacity building in Open Science, thereby supporting the creation of a more transparent, collaborative, and sustainable research ecosystem between the EU and LAC.

2. COURSE OBJECTIVES

General Objective:

The objective of this e-learning course is to train participants in Open Science principles and practices, focusing on its role in addressing critical issues such as climate change and environmental degradation. Participants can explore tools, platforms, and methods for fostering collaboration, ensuring inclusivity, and accelerating scientific discovery while gaining insights into Open Science's potential to promote sustainable solutions.

Specific Objectives:

Building on the general goal of promoting Open Science practices within the context of the energy transition, natural capital, and climate change, this course pursues the following specific objectives:

1. **Promote understanding of Open Science principles and policies** within the European and Latin American and Caribbean contexts, emphasizing their role in advancing sustainable research and innovation.
2. **Introduce participants to key Open Science tools and infrastructures**, including open data repositories, collaborative platforms, and open-access publishing systems relevant to environmental and energy research.
3. **Strengthen participants' capacity to apply Open Science methodologies** in their own research, promoting transparency, reproducibility, and interdisciplinary collaboration.
4. **Encourage the integration of citizen science and participatory approaches**, facilitating broader engagement of society in environmental and climate-related research.
5. **Demonstrate practical examples and case studies** that show how Open Science accelerates knowledge transfer, fosters innovation, and supports evidence-based policymaking for the energy transition and environmental sustainability.

3. TARGET AUDIENCE

The course is tailored for a diverse range of participants, including researchers, research infrastructure personnel, public administrators, civil society representatives, and private sector stakeholders from LAC and the EU with an interest in Open Science and its applications to the energy transition, natural capital, and climate change.

To maximize accessibility and ensure effective participation, the course materials are offered primarily in Spanish and English.

4. COURSE STRUCTURE AND CONTENT OVERVIEW

The course is structured into four modules. The introductory module focuses on UNESCO's Open Science recommendations, and provides an overview of the current state of Open Science in Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean, as well as the role of key research infrastructures in fostering open and collaborative scientific ecosystems.

The following three modules address essential dimensions of Open Science:

- Challenges for monitoring and evaluating science through Open Science sources
- Open scientific knowledge
- Open participation of social actors

Each module is structured around a series of sessions led by distinguished experts in their respective fields, combining conceptual foundations with practical examples. The program features 15 instructors in total: 7 from LAC (Costa Rica, Argentina and Chile) and 8 from the EU (Portugal, Romania and Spain) providing participants with diverse perspectives and hands-on guidance to effectively integrate Open Science principles into their research and professional practice.

Module 1: Open Science and major global challenges

This introductory module explores how Open Science practices can act as powerful enablers to address major global challenges, including the climate crisis, environmental degradation, and the pursuit of the Sustainable Development Goals.

Through a series of expert-led seminars focusing on LAC and the EU, participants examine how Open Science accelerates scientific discovery, fosters international collaboration, enhances research visibility and career development, and strengthens the connection between science, policy, and society. The module also highlights the policy frameworks and initiatives shaping Open Science in both regions, offering a comparative view of their progress, priorities, and challenges.

Module 1 consists of three thematic sessions delivered by three experts:

1. **Contribution of Open Science to address major global challenges** – *Guillermo Anlló (UNESCO, Costa Rica)* An overview of the role of Open Science as a transformative mechanism for tackling global environmental and societal issues through openness, inclusivity, and knowledge sharing, including introducing participants to UNESCO's Open Science recommendation.
2. **Status of Open Science in the European Union and OpenAIRE** – *Giulia Malanguarnera (Universidade do Minho / OpenAIRE, Portugal)* Presentation of the European Open Science framework, including policies, infrastructures, and the role of OpenAIRE in supporting open access, open data, and reproducible research.

3. **Status of Open Science in Latin America and the Caribbean** – *Andrea Mora Campos (Universidad Nacional de Costa Rica)* Provide an overview of the current state of Open Science regulations and initiatives in Latin America, including key policies, national strategies, and regional programs that promote open access to research outputs, data sharing, and collaborative scientific practices.

Module 2: Challenges for monitoring and evaluating science through Open Science sources

This module examines the challenges and opportunities associated with monitoring and evaluating scientific progress through Open Science sources, emphasizing how open practices can transform traditional research assessment frameworks. It highlights the need to move beyond conventional metrics, such as impact factors, towards more inclusive, transparent, and impact-oriented evaluation approaches.

Participants explore how Open Science contributes to greater collaboration, knowledge sharing, and visibility within the scientific community, particularly benefiting early-career researchers by creating more equitable and accessible research environments. The module also presents the strategic role of RedCLARA and the BELLA II Project in enhancing digital research infrastructures in Latin America, enabling interoperability, connectivity, and data accessibility essential for Open Science advancement.

Module 2 consists of three thematic sessions delivered by three experts:

1. **Benefits of Open Science for the scientific community and early-career researchers** – *Allan Campos (CeNAT, Costa Rica)* Exploration of how Open Science enhances professional development, fosters inclusion, and provides new avenues for collaboration and recognition among researchers.
2. **Open Science publication impact and methods of quality assessment** – *Radu Vasile (Politehnica University of Timisoara, Romania)* Introduction to the principles and benefits of Open Access publishing. It covers the differences between Open Access and Open Data, explores Gold and Green publishing models, and presents practical examples of implementation to enhance research visibility. It includes a discussion on the advantages and challenges of adopting Open Access in participant's work.
3. **Digital infrastructure and Open Science: RedCLARA and BELLA II as drivers of the scientific ecosystem in Latin America** – *Tania Altamirano (RedCLARA, Chile)* Exploration of the strategic role of RedCLARA and the BELLA II Project in strengthening Latin America's research infrastructure to support Open Science. It also emphasizes the importance of connectivity, advanced computing, and interoperability in fostering a collaborative digital scientific ecosystem.

Module 3: Open scientific knowledge

This module explores the concept of Open Scientific Knowledge, the unrestricted access to and reuse of scientific outputs, including publications, research data, metadata, educational resources, software, source code, and even hardware. It also addresses the growing importance of transparency in research methodologies and evaluation processes.

Through a combination of theoretical and practical sessions, participants discover key Open Science practices for sharing knowledge across disciplines, focusing particularly on open-access publications, research data sharing, and open-source software development. Real-world examples illustrate how these practices foster collaboration, innovation, and reproducibility in the fields of biodiversity and energy research.

The module also introduces participants to a selection of widely used Open Science tools, platforms, and repositories, highlighting their application in promoting openness, interoperability, and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles in scientific work.

Module 3 consists of five thematic sessions delivered by five experts in the respective fields:

1. **Open Science and Open-Source software** – *Kevin Moraga García (Instituto Tecnológico de Costa Rica)* An introduction to the principles of Open Science and open-source software, exploring their shared philosophy of transparency, collaboration, and community-driven innovation
2. **Open Science tools and how to use them** – *Diana Andone (Politehnica University of Timisoara, Rumania)* A general overview of open-access tools, repositories, and publication platforms that enable researchers to share and manage their scientific outputs effectively.
3. **Open-Source technological tools: use cases in energy transition (PREDICO, INTERSTORE, INTERCONNECT)** – *Ricardo Andrade, Alexandre Lucas, Carlos Silva (INESCTEC, Portugal)* Presentation of concrete applications of open-source technologies in the field of energy transition, demonstrating how openness accelerates scientific progress.
4. **Open Science and biodiversity: Overcoming challenges and exploring new opportunities** – *Francisco Pando (GBIF, Spain)* An introduction to the role of Open Science in advancing biodiversity research, addressing barriers, and highlighting emerging opportunities for collaboration and data sharing.
5. **Open and FAIR Science tools and use cases** – *Julio Paneque (LifeWatch ERIC, Spain)* An exploration of tools and infrastructures designed to support open and FAIR science, with specific examples on biodiversity and energy transition that demonstrate how these principles enhance the visibility, reproducibility, and long-term impact of scientific research.

Module 4: Open participation of social actors

This module examines how Open Science extends beyond the scientific community by fostering collaboration between researchers and diverse social actors, including citizens, local communities, policymakers, and entrepreneurs. It explores how open participation transforms the research process into a more inclusive, transparent, and socially responsive endeavor.

Participants learn how different forms of engagement, such as citizen science, empower society to take part in knowledge generation and shared problem-solving. By integrating scientific, local, and indigenous knowledge systems, Open Science builds trust, promotes co-creation, and ensures that research outcomes reflect real-world needs and values.

The module also emphasizes the role of Open Science in strengthening dialogue among scientists, policymakers, professionals, and communities, giving all stakeholders a voice in shaping the direction and impact of research.

Module 4 consists of two thematic sessions delivered by two experts in the field:

1. **Integration of scientific, local, and indigenous knowledge** – *Rafael Corrales (Associate Project Officer, Natural Sciences, UNESCO, Costa Rica)* An introduction to inclusive knowledge systems and the importance of integrating diverse epistemologies into research processes to enhance relevance, legitimacy, and sustainability. It provides an overview of international legislation on Indigenous Peoples, explores the contribution of nature-based solutions from indigenous perspectives, and analyzes regional case studies to understand how traditional knowledge supports effective and sustainable climate action.
2. **Citizen Science Experiences** – *Valeria Arza (Universidad Nacional de San Martín, Argentina)* An introduction to the citizen science approach, highlighting its potential to generate knowledge and serve as a tool for social and scientific transformation. It explores

citizen science projects across diverse disciplines, examines global policy tools that support its development, and assesses the broader benefits of public engagement in research.

5. VIRTUAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENT IMPLEMENTATION

The e-learning course was developed using a blended learning methodology, integrating in-person instructional activities with online learning. The face-to-face sessions enable direct interaction with instructors and peers, the immediate resolution of questions, and the completion of practical activities that require guidance. In parallel, the virtual environment allows students to progress at their own pace, access materials at any time, develop autonomy, and take advantage of interactive digital resources that enrich the learning experience.

The course is supported by Moodle, a robust, scalable, and user-friendly platform selected for its flexibility, compatibility with multimedia resources, and ability to comprehensively manage both the course and student participation. Moodle's interface enables participants to easily navigate modules, track their progress, and access resources in an organized manner. As an online learning platform (LMS, Learning Management System), Moodle is free and open-source software, which allows it to be adapted to the specific requirements of the course.

5.1. Platform Structure and Organization

All course materials are organized in Moodle using a modular structure. Each module consists of several sessions that include the following sections (Figures 1 and 2):

- **Instructor profile:** A brief description of the session's instructor, including their institutional affiliation, area of expertise, and role in the course. This provides participants with a clear context about the speakers and their contributions.
- **Session objectives:** A summary of the learning goals guiding each session.
- **Session recordings:** Full videos of live classes and presentations, available for asynchronous review.
- **Presentation slides:** Downloadable materials used during live sessions.
- **Supporting resources:** Supplementary documents, guides, datasets, and links to external resources that enrich the learning process.
- **Assigned readings:** Each module includes high-value readings and resources that complement the content covered in the sessions. These materials allow participants to deepen their understanding of key concepts, consolidate learning, and encourage independent study. All readings are downloadable, facilitating offline access. Their purpose is to provide a solid theoretical foundation, promote critical thinking, and support the development of skills for practical application of the knowledge gained.
- **Quiz:** At the end of each session, a short self-assessment quiz is included to reinforce key concepts. This tool allows participants to immediately gauge their level of understanding, identify areas of uncertainty, and recognize topics that require further review. Additionally, it provides valuable feedback for course organizers, as it helps evaluate the clarity of the content, the effectiveness of teaching strategies, and the extent to which learning objectives are being met. The results are used to make adjustments, improve future sessions, and ensure that the training process addresses the real needs of participants.

Biography

Giulia Malaguarnera is an expert in Open Science policy and infrastructure, currently serving as Outreach and Engagement Officer at OpenAIRE. With a PhD in Neuropharmacology and extensive experience in European research projects, she works at the intersection of science policy, innovation, and community engagement. Giulia leads capacity-building initiatives to help researchers, institutions, and funders implement Open Science practices aligned with European and international frameworks. She is actively involved in the Horizon Europe project GraspOS, which focuses on reforming research assessment through open and responsible practices. Giulia also collaborates with partners in Latin America, North America, and Asia to promote global dialogue and the adoption of Open Science across diverse research systems.

Biografía

Giulia Malaguarnera es experta en políticas de Ciencia Abierta e infraestructuras, actualmente se desempeña como Responsable de Difusión y Participación en OpenAIRE. Con un doctorado en Neurofarmacología y una amplia experiencia en proyectos de investigación europeos, trabaja en la intersección entre política científica, innovación y participación comunitaria.

Giulia lidera iniciativas de capacitación para ayudar a investigadores, instituciones y financiadores a implementar prácticas de Ciencia Abierta alineadas con marcos europeos e internacionales. Participa activamente en el proyecto GraspOS de Horizonte Europa, que se centra en la reforma de la evaluación de la investigación mediante prácticas abiertas y responsables. Colabora con socios en América Latina, Norteamérica y Asia para promover el diálogo global y la adopción de la Ciencia Abierta en diversos sistemas de investigación.

General Objective:

Enable participants to understand and implement Open Science practices within the European research ecosystem, with a focus on policy, infrastructure, and practical tools.

Specific Objectives:

- Identify key components and goals of the European Open Science strategy.
- Distinguish between open access, open data, and open software in research workflows.
- Explore the role of OpenAIRE as a support infrastructure for Open Science.
- Learn how to discover and share open research outputs relevant to climate change and sustainability.
- Understand the broader societal and economic benefits of open, transparent, and reproducible science.

Objetivo General:

Permitir a los participantes comprender e implementar prácticas de Ciencia Abierta dentro del ecosistema europeo de investigación, con un enfoque en políticas, infraestructuras y herramientas prácticas.

Objetivos Específicos:

- Identificar los componentes clave y las metas de la estrategia europea de Ciencia Abierta.
- Distinguir entre acceso abierto, datos abiertos y software abierto en los flujos de trabajo de investigación.
- Explorar el papel de OpenAIRE como infraestructura de apoyo para la Ciencia Abierta.
- Aprender a descubrir y compartir resultados de investigación abierta relevantes para el cambio climático y la sostenibilidad.
- Comprender los beneficios sociales y económicos más amplios de una ciencia abierta, transparente y reproducible.

Figure 1. above) Overview of the general Moodle environment; below) section of the Moodle platform displaying the instructor's biography and the session objectives, in Spanish and English.

Figure 2. Section of the Moodle platform displaying the materials and recordings of the session.

5.2. Access and user management

Participants have individual, secure user accounts to access the Moodle platform. Access is granted through a standard login process aligned with security best practices, ensuring the protection of user data, system integrity, and traceability of activities within the platform. This login step is required to maintain a secure and reliable environment but does not restrict access, as any user can freely register and obtain credentials without additional validation.

To register, users must go to the “Register as a user” section (see Figure 3), complete the required information, and submit their request. Access is granted immediately upon registration, without the need for manual review or approval, enabling direct and open entry to the platform.

User roles are assigned according to Moodle standards. Instructors and administrators have full permissions to create and manage content according to the course structure, while participants have access to all learning materials, resources, and communication tools. Each instructor is provided with a dedicated space within the platform to design and upload content following the established methodology.

To access the online course, users must visit the official website:

<https://moodlecenat.org/moodle/login/index.php?loginredirect=1>

[Español - Internacional \(es\)](#) ▾

Acceder

[¿Olvidó su contraseña?](#)

Registrarse como usuario

Para acceder a esta página debe crear una cuenta primero.

[Aviso de Cookies](#)

Figure 3. Log-in and registration system

Upon registering or logging in, users gain access to the main page of the Moodle platform, where they can find a description of the course and links to the different modules that make it up (Figure 4).

La pérdida de recursos naturales y su estabilidad fluctuante se han convertido en una preocupación global que debe abordarse como una prioridad, ya que los desafíos ambientales son cada vez más frecuentes cada año. El cambio climático está generando presiones sobre muchos recursos naturales, alterando la funcionalidad de los ecosistemas e influyendo en la pérdida de biodiversidad. En este contexto crítico, la ciencia abierta se destaca como un enfoque transformador que acelera la investigación y fomenta la colaboración para enfrentar los desafíos ambientales, conectando a la comunidad científica con políticas responsables y la participación activa de la ciudadanía.

La ciencia abierta impulsa la innovación, permitiendo el desarrollo de soluciones sostenibles frente a los problemas ambientales más urgentes. Su enfoque colaborativo integra conocimientos científicos de alto nivel entre disciplinas, haciendo que las soluciones sean más accesibles y con mayor impacto. La ciencia abierta garantiza la calidad y la disponibilidad continua de los datos necesarios para monitorear y abordar la degradación ambiental. También permite la participación de la ciencia ciudadana, contribuyendo a la recopilación de datos de interés y a la creación de bases de datos globales. Este curso está dirigido a profesionales de distintas disciplinas, con el propósito de ampliar, comunicar e integrar conocimientos que aborden los desafíos ambientales globales urgentes. A medida que estos desafíos aumentan en escala y frecuencia, el curso ofrece una variedad de herramientas y perspectivas necesarias para impulsar un cambio positivo y fomentar el progreso sostenible.

El proyecto EnergyTRAN tiene como objetivo abordar el desafío común de la transición energética promoviendo el intercambio, la generación y la transferencia de conocimientos entre infraestructuras de investigación de la Unión Europea (UE) y de América Latina y el Caribe (ALC), desde una perspectiva multidisciplinaria que incluye aspectos tecnológicos, ambientales y sociales. Como parte de esta iniciativa, se está organizando un curso en línea para explorar cómo la ciencia abierta puede contribuir a enfrentar los principales desafíos ambientales fomentando la colaboración y el intercambio de conocimientos entre científicos, instituciones y la sociedad en su conjunto.

Energytran

Categorías

- [Módulo 1: Ciencia abierta y los grandes desafíos globales.](#) ⁽³⁾
- [Módulo 2: Desafíos para el monitoreo y la evaluación de la ciencia a través de fuentes de ciencia abierta.](#) ⁽³⁾
- [Módulo 3: Conocimiento científico abierto Parte A](#) ⁽³⁾
- [Módulo 3: Conocimiento científico abierto Parte B](#) ⁽²⁾
- [Módulo 4: Participación abierta de los actores sociales.](#) ⁽²⁾

Expandir todo

Figure 4. Main page of the e-learning course Moodle platform

Once inside a module, users can access the various sessions it contains (Figures 5 to 9). Within each session, they have access to all related information and materials as described in section 4.1., including the instructor's profile, the objective of the session, session recordings, presentation slides, supporting resources and a self-assessment quiz.

Cursos / Módulo 1: Ciencia abierta y los grandes desafíos globales.

Módulo 1: Ciencia abierta y los grandes desafíos globales.

Categoría Papelera de reciclaje Subir cursos Más ▾

Módulo 1: Ciencia abierta y los grandes desafíos globales. Buscar cursos Q

Estado de la ciencia abierta en la UE. OpenAIRE

Profesor: [Giulia Malaguarnera](#)

Contribución de la ciencia abierta para abordar los grandes desafíos globales

Profesor: [Guillermo Anlló](#)

Estado de la ciencia abierta en ALC

Profesor: [Andrea Mora Campos](#)

Figure 5. Access to the three sessions within module 1 “Open Science and major global challenges”

Cursos / Módulo 2: Desafíos para el monitoreo y la evaluación de la ciencia a través de fuentes de ciencia abierta.

Módulo 2: Desafíos para el monitoreo y la evaluación de la ciencia a través de fuentes de ciencia abierta.

Categoría Subir cursos Más ▾

Módulo 2: Desafíos para el monitoreo y la evaluación de la ciencia a través de fuentes de ciencia abierta. Buscar cursos Q

Infraestructura Digital y Ciencia Abierta

[Infraestructura Digital y Ciencia Abierta: RedCLARA y BELLA II como impulsores del ecosistema científico en América Latina y el Caribe](#)

Profesor: [Tania Altamirano](#)

Descripción del curso

Impacto de las publicaciones en ciencia abierta y métodos de calidad

[Impacto de las publicaciones en ciencia abierta y métodos de calidad](#)

Profesor: [Radu Vasiliu](#)

Descripción del curso

Beneficios de la ciencia abierta para la comunidad científica y los investigadores en etapa inicial

[Beneficios de la ciencia abierta para la comunidad científica y los investigadores en etapa inicial](#)

Profesor: [Allan Campos](#)

Descripción del curso

Figure 6. Access to the three sessions within module 2 “Challenges for monitoring and evaluating science through Open Science sources”

Cursos / Módulo 3: Conocimiento científico abierto Parte A

Módulo 3: Conocimiento científico abierto Parte A

Categoría Subir cursos Más ▾

Módulo 3: Conocimiento científico abierto Parte A

Ciencia Abierta y software de código abierto
Profesor: [Kevin Moraga García](#)

Herramientas de ciencia abierta y cómo utilizarlas (herramientas, repositorios, publicaciones)
Profesor: [Diana Andone](#)

Herramientas tecnológicas de código abierto: casos de uso (PREDICO, INTERSTORE, INTERCONNECT)
Profesor: [Ricardo Andrade](#)
Profesor: [Alexandre Lucas](#)
Profesor: [Carlos Silva](#)

Figure 7. Access to the first three sessions within module 3 “Open scientific knowledge”

Cursos / Módulo 3: Conocimiento científico abierto Parte B

Módulo 3: Conocimiento científico abierto Parte B

Categoría Subir cursos Más ▾

Módulo 3: Conocimiento científico abierto Parte B

Ciencia abierta y biodiversidad: superando desafíos y explorando nuevas oportunidades
Profesor: [Francisco Pando](#)

Herramientas de ciencia abierta y FAIR y casos de uso (Energytran Network4Collaboration y workflows)
Profesor: [Julio Paneque](#)

Figure 8. Access to the last two sessions within module 3 “Open scientific knowledge”

[Cursos](#) / Módulo 4: Participación abierta de los actores sociales.

Módulo 4: Participación abierta de los actores sociales.

The screenshot displays the course selection interface for 'Módulo 4: Participación abierta de los actores sociales'. At the top, there are navigation links: 'Cursos', 'Módulo 4: Participación abierta de los actores sociales.', 'Categoría', 'Papelerera de reciclaje', 'Subir cursos', and 'Más'. Below this is a search bar containing the module name and a 'Buscar cursos' button with a magnifying glass icon. Two course cards are visible:

- Card 1:** 'Introducción general - Integración del conocimiento científico, local e indígena'. The professor is Rafael Corrales. There is a 'Descripción del curso' button below the card.
- Card 2:** 'Experiencia de Ciencia Ciudadana'. The professor is Valeria Arza.

Figure 9. Access to the two sessions within module 4 “Open participation of social actors”

6. RESULTS OF THE PILOT E-LEARNING COURSE

6.1 Pilot overview

The pilot implementation of the Open Science e-Learning course took place in San José, Costa Rica, from 22 to 26 September 2025, following a hybrid format that combined both in-person and virtual participation. The course comprised a total of 20 hours of instruction over five consecutive days (4 hours per day).

Given the participation of instructors and attendees from multiple LAC and EU countries, the schedule was carefully designed to accommodate the time zones of both regions: 8:00 AM - 12:00 PM (GMT-6) / 4:00 PM – 8:00 PM (CET).

6.2 Language and accessibility

The main language of instruction was Spanish, ensuring accessibility for most participants from Latin America. However, communication in Portuguese and English was also supported, with simultaneous interpretation available in all three languages throughout the sessions. This multilingual approach promoted inclusivity and strengthened cross-regional collaboration between LAC and EU participants.

6.3 Methodology and learning approach

The course was conducted under a blended learning modality through the Moodle platform, combining virtual activities and face-to-face sessions to offer a flexible, dynamic, and student-centered learning environment. This methodology allowed for the integration of synchronous and asynchronous moments, enabling participants to engage actively according to their own schedules, needs, and learning pace.

In the virtual component, the Moodle platform served as the central coordinating hub, providing access to resources, activities, and spaces for interaction. The Zoom tool complemented this environment, facilitating video conferencing sessions, collaborative work, and practical experiences that strengthened the joint construction of knowledge.

The face-to-face activities reinforced the learning developed online, promoting direct exchange and the application of content in real-world contexts. This combination fostered a comprehensive learning experience characterized by flexibility, continuous participation, and ongoing support.

Additionally, each session included a self-assessment questionnaire, allowing participants to monitor their progress, identify strengths and areas for improvement, and consolidate the knowledge acquired. Overall, the blended learning approach not only expanded opportunities for access and participation but also enhanced autonomous learning, meaningful interaction, and the development of digital and collaborative competencies.

6.4 Dissemination and communication strategy

The communication and dissemination strategy for the e-learning course held in Costa Rica was designed as a multi-layered effort, activated well before the course began. In the initial phase, project partners were mobilized to support the outreach process within their respective networks, ensuring that information about the course reached relevant academic, institutional, and technical audiences across the region. At the same time, Lifewatch and the OEI amplified the visibility of the event by circulating the course announcement and registration link through its established distribution lists, which significantly broadened the scope of the call.

Because the e-learning course offered both onsite and virtual participation, and places were limited, the communication campaign unfolded over an extended period to reach a wide yet targeted audience. Once the registration deadline closed, a careful selection process was launched to identify participants for both modalities. The overwhelming number of applications received far surpassed the available places—a clear indicator of the course's relevance and the strong interest it generated among professionals and stakeholders. This high level of demand, particularly from those who were ultimately unable to secure a spot, provided organizers with valuable insight into the real market appetite for such training and reinforced the importance of offering similar opportunities in the future.

During the delivery of the course, a dedicated photojournalist was engaged to visually document the launch, the thematic sessions, and the field visits that formed part of the official programme. Beyond capturing the key moments, the photographer also produced a series of short video capsules featuring participants who followed the course throughout its full duration. These testimonials highlighted the value of the training, the commitment of those involved, and the broader significance of promoting open science in the context of global environmental challenges. The audiovisual material served not only as a record of the event but also as an effective communication tool to expand its visibility.

Finally, both the launch and the subsequent sessions were widely disseminated through the communication channels of the consortium partners—particularly LifeWatch, CENAT, and the OEI. Updates were published on institutional websites, shared through social media platforms, and compiled on the project’s official webpage. These publications contributed to maintaining momentum and ensuring that the course’s objectives and achievements reached an international audience.

Examples of this dissemination include:

- <https://energytran.oei.int/the-energytran-project-launches-an-international-course-to-advance-in-open-science-face-of-global-environmental-challenges/>
- <https://energytran.oei.int/gbif-spain-drives-open-science-and-sustainability-within-the-framework-of-the-energytran-project/>

6.5 Participant engagement

A total of 115 individuals from more than 20 countries (Latin-American and European countries) expressed interest in participating in the pilot edition of the e-Learning course. After applying the selection criteria, 15 participants attended in person in San José (Costa Rica) while 18 joined online through the Zoom platform. Participants were selected taking into account a brief resume included on the application form ([Application form - Course: Environmental challenges and open science](#)). 83% of applicants wanted to participate in the course in a virtual way.

The target audience comprised a diverse range of stakeholders, including: Researchers and academics (Master’s students, PhD candidates, postdoctoral researchers, and senior scientists), Research infrastructure and data management professionals, Representatives of public administration and policy institutions, Members of civil society organizations, and Private sector actors engaged in Open Science, energy, and biodiversity initiatives.

At the end of the course, a total of 16 participants successfully completed all required activities and received an official Certificate of Completion issued by the project Coordinators (OEI). In addition, 17 researchers, technical and support people were involved in the pilot course.

6.6. Participant satisfaction survey

At the end of the pilot e-Learning course, participants completed a satisfaction survey aimed at evaluating the overall quality, relevance, and effectiveness of the training. The survey covered five key dimensions: course content, structure and format, instructors, logistics and communication, and overall impact and usefulness. A total of 22 responses were received (detailed responses to the satisfaction survey can be seen in Annex I).

Overall assessment: The results show a high level of satisfaction, with 96% of participants rating the overall quality of the course as “good” or “very good.” Respondents highlighted the relevance of the topics, the quality of instruction, and the impact and usefulness of the course.

Course content: Participants positively evaluated the relevance and applicability of the topics addressed, with 72-77% expressing agreement or strong agreement across content-related

indicators. The examples and case studies were considered useful and applicable (72.8%), while the materials and resources available on the Moodle platform were rated as adequate (77.3%).

Structure and format: The organization and logical sequence of modules were among the best-rated aspects, with 85.7% of participants agreeing that the progression of topics facilitated understanding, and 77.2% acknowledging the clarity and coherence of the course structure.

The duration of sessions was considered appropriate by 72.7% and the hybrid format was positively received (68.1%). The Moodle platform was valued as a useful tool (72.7%), and simultaneous translation was appreciated by 68.2%, confirming the multilingual approach as an asset for cross-regional participation.

Instructors: The performance of instructors received strongly positive feedback, with 81.8% agreeing that explanations were clear and engagement levels appropriate. However, 19% felt that there could be more opportunities for questions and discussion, suggesting that future editions may benefit from extended interactive segments.

Logistics and communication: Logistical and communication aspects were generally well evaluated. Participants found coordination adequate (77.3%) and the schedule convenient (81.8%). However, awareness and outreach could be improved: only 54.5% found it easy to learn about the course's existence, and half of the participants heard about it via email, with less visibility through the website, the newsletter, social networks, or other channels.

Impact and usefulness: The course achieved its objectives, with 72.7% of participants indicating that it provided new, applicable knowledge and tools. A similar proportion expressed interest in the topics addressed and stated that they would recommend the course to others (72.7%), confirming the perceived value and relevance of the training.

The insights collected through this survey provide valuable input for refining future editions of the e-Learning Course, helping to enhance the learning experience, optimize content delivery, and strengthen participant engagement.

7. CONCLUSION

The Energytran e-Learning Course “*Environmental Challenges and Open Science – An Approach from Innovation and Technology*” provides a validated, high-quality training resource that promotes Open Science principles in the context of energy transition and environmental sustainability across EU and LAC regions. The course demonstrates the feasibility of hybrid, multilingual delivery and offers participants relevant, clear, and practically applicable content. As a reusable and scalable resource, it fosters transparency, collaboration, and societal impact in research, supporting cross-regional knowledge exchange and the advancement of Open Science to address global environmental challenges.

8. ANNEXES

Annex I. RESULTS OF THE SATISFACTION SURVEY

Contents of the course

In the figures below, the y-axis represents the number of responses received, while the x-axis corresponds to the different categories, where 1 means “strongly agree” and 5 means “strongly disagree.”

Los contenidos abordaron temas relevantes para mi trabajo o intereses.

22 respuestas

El nivel de profundidad de los contenidos fue adecuado.

22 respuestas

Los ejemplos y casos prácticos fueron útiles y aplicables.

22 respuestas

Los materiales y recursos disponibles en la plataforma de aprendizaje son adecuados.

22 respuestas

Structure and format of the course

In the figures below, the y-axis represents the number of responses received, while the x-axis corresponds to the different categories, where 1 means “strongly agree” and 5 means “strongly disagree.”

La estructura de los módulos y contenidos fue clara y coherente.

22 respuestas

La secuencia de temas facilitó la comprensión global del curso.

21 respuestas

La duración de las sesiones fue adecuada.

22 respuestas

La modalidad híbrida (presencial + online) funcionó bien.

22 respuestas

La plataforma de aprendizaje Moodle fue de utilidad.

22 respuestas

El idioma y la traducción simultánea facilitaron la comprensión de los contenidos.

22 respuestas

Instructors of the course

In the figures below, the y-axis represents the number of responses received, while the x-axis corresponds to the different categories, where 1 means “strongly agree” and 5 means “strongly disagree.”

La explicación de los contenidos fue clara.

22 respuestas

El nivel de implicación fue adecuado.

22 respuestas

Hubo suficiente espacio para preguntas y discusión.

21 respuestas

Communication and logistics

In the figures below, the y-axis represents the number of responses received, while the x-axis corresponds to the different categories, where 1 means “strongly agree” and 5 means “strongly disagree.”

Ha sido fácil conocer la existencia del curso.

22 respuestas

La información previa al curso (programa, agenda, accesos, sistema de inscripción) fue clara y suficiente.

22 respuestas

La selección de los participantes siguió unos criterios adecuados.

22 respuestas

La coordinación general del curso fue adecuada.

22 respuestas

El horario y calendario se ajustaron a mis posibilidades.

22 respuestas

¿Cómo conoció la existencia del curso?

Impact and usefulness

In the figures below, the y-axis represents the number of responses received, while the x-axis corresponds to the different categories, where 1 means “strongly agree” and 5 means “strongly disagree.”

Considero que el curso me ha proporcionado nuevas herramientas y conocimientos aplicables.

22 respuestas

Los temas tratados han sido de interés.

22 respuestas

Recomendaría este curso a otras personas.

22 respuestas

¿Cómo valorarías la calidad general del curso?

Annex II. COURSE MATERIALS

All materials developed for the course are structured and available on the Moodle platform (<https://moodlecenat.org/moodle/>). Materials that can be exported in PDF format are attached to this deliverable, while video content remains accessible directly through the platform.

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www.energytran.oei.int

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Status of Open Science in the EU and the Role of OpenAIRE

Giulia Malaguarnera

Financiado por
la Unión Europea

Open Science

Global and in Europe

About this session

Open Science in Europe and OpenAIRE

Session overview

- Open Science in the EU: evolving landscape & daily relevance for research.
- Goes beyond Open Access → includes data, software, reproducible methods.
- European policy framework & practical tools for transparency and impact.
- OpenAIRE Graph & CONNECT as examples: fostering discovery across domains (e.g., climate & energy).
- Focus on **capacity building**: empowering participants to adopt and advocate Open Science.

Learning Objectives

General Objective:

- Understand and implement Open Science practices in the EU research ecosystem.

Specific Objectives:

- Identify key components and goals of the EU Open Science strategy.
- Distinguish between Open Access, Open Data, Open Software.
- Explore the role of **OpenAIRE** in supporting Open Science.
- Learn how to discover & share outputs (climate & sustainability examples).
- Recognize the societal and economic benefits of Open Science.

An introduction

Open Science

Open Science is transforming the way research is conducted and shared **globally and in Europe**. It goes beyond Open Access to include open data, software, and reproducible methodologies, supported by international initiatives and strong European policies. This session explores how the global **Open Science** movement and the European agenda converge, and how infrastructures enable researchers to make their work more transparent, collaborative, and impactful for science, society, and the economy.

UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science

Definition of Open Science

- **Beyond** Open Access to Publications
- Collaboration & Interdisciplinarity
- New functional and organisational schemes

<https://www.unesco.org/en/natural-sciences/open-science>

Open Science: a few facts and truths

- Open Science is here to stay
- Open Science is multifaceted
- Open Science costs. Needs long term investments
- Institutional approach is crucially important to make Open Science happen
- Open Science requires a holistic approach: **tools, incentives, and assessment** to become a win-win for all
- Putting the researcher in the middle is the holy grail: but we need to target all other actors in the research ecosystem

Open Science in Europe: The Journey

European Research Area, Recommendations for MS

- **Open Science policies popping up**
 - Different flavours from OA to publications, to Open Data
 - Both for funding and research performing organisations
- **Intense funding for infrastructure for Open Science**
 - PIDs, repositories, OA Journals
 - Software is becoming the new hot topic
 - European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) National Nodes under consideration
- **European Data Spaces**
 - Providing access to commercial, public & research data
 - Ministries are signing commitments to support 9 data spaces (EOSC one of them)

European Research Area
(ERA)*

20 action points

Open Science & EOSC is #1

ERA Monitor Watch

Recommendations for MS on
monitoring Open Science

Open Access to Publications. Data a first class-citizen

Goals

- Free flow of information
- Data sovereignty

Laws & regulations

- European Data Act
- European Data Governance Act
- European strategy for data
- EU Copyright Law
- EU wide Secondary Publishing Rights (SPR) → translates to immediate OA
- EU AI Act

“Unless you go for a patent or you have a concrete exploitation plan, I would say that the reuse of data with citations brings value to the researcher as individual and the community”

Prodromos Tsiavos,

Episode #6, OpenAIRE Podcast

Next generation metrics where Open Science has a key role

- Measuring a diverse range of research outputs (publications, research data, software, ...)
- Assessing based on Open Science practices
- Using Open Infrastructures for bibliometric/scientometric assessment

Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment

Our vision is that the assessment of research, researchers and research organisations recognises the diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research. This requires basing assessment primarily on qualitative judgement, for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.

500 + signatories

The European Commission instruments for OS

Open Research Europe in Action

Efficient

- Rigorous open peer review
- Rapid and transparent
- International scientific advisory board

Impactful

- Immediate open access
- Article-level metrics
- Open data for reproducibility and reuse

Stress-free

- Optional service*
- No administrative burden
- No author fees
- Automatic compliance with open access requirements

** Service available also after grant has ended*

Open Research Europe

European Open Science Cloud =

E-Infrastructure consolidation

Enable researchers to access data, storage and compute ("cloud") via an Europe wide federation of IT services ("e-Infrastructure")

Open Science

Drive the transition to Open Science (Open Data, Open Standards, Open Literature) - bring research benefits to European societies at large

Scientific Communities' content and user

Populate EOCS with the scientific data resources and computational tools from research infrastructures - drive usage by to Europe's 1.7 M researchers

Logos included: ENVRI, SSHOC, EOSC-Life, panOSC, ESCAPE, E-Infrastructure, Open Science, Scientific Communities' content and user.

The European Commission instruments for OS

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=67mirPt-FhY>

<https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>

What's OpenAIRE?

Status of Open Science in the EU and the Role of OpenAIRE

About OpenAIRE

Scholarly Communication e-infrastructure

- Non-profit organisation, established **Oct 2018**
- **Mission:** Shift scholarly communication towards openness and transparency and facilitate innovative ways to communicate and monitor research
- A **Scholarly Communication e-Infrastructure** that brings together **human capital** and advanced **ICT services**
- A **network of experts** from major national organisations (National Open Access Desks) in operation since 2009

Global Collaborations: Latin America, US, Canada, Japan, Korea, ...

NEW WAYS OF PERFORMING SCIENCE

Everything is digital
Everything is big
Everything is connected

Research life cycle is interconnected, and openness has a positive affect in every stage

Transition To an Open ecosystem that will support Diversity – Equity - Inclusion

What's at stake

Services

Connecting

- *Establishing infrastructure*
- *Added value services*

Aligning

- *Standard*
- *Guidelines*
- *Practices*
- *Workflows*

Policies

Training

Empowering:

- *Open Science*
- *Open Access*
- *Policies*
- *Services*

How OpenAIRE Helps?

With Services and a pool of Experts

helpdesk@openaire.eu

Key services to support the transition to Open Science

Status of Open Science in the EU and the Role of OpenAIRE

- **A way to support and track Open Science from the onset**
- **mandatory by research funders.**
- **Emerging as an integral part of the research ecosystem with lots of automations to make it easy for everyone to use.**

- 1** Use directly via Argos website
argos.openaire.eu
- 2** Implement a local installation of Argos in your organisation (local premises)
- 3** Request a white labelled installation of Argos, including personalised support and training.

OpenAIRE Graph: a 360° view of research enabled by an interconnected ecosystem of research results.

Onboarded Data Sources

Repositories Publishers
OA Journals Registries
Aggregators CRIS

Notable examples:

Instrumental Data Sources

From OpenAIRE partners:

Funder databases

graph.openaire.eu

OpenAIRE Graph

Datasets & APIs

explore.openaire.eu

Turn Open Science into Practice with CONNECT

Empower your research community with a gateway that does more than just showcasing outputs. Facilitate the discovery, connection, and linking of research products that matter most to you and your audiences. Transform your vision of Open Science into a tangible, operational reality.

Discover and outreach

ON-demand dashboards providing timely, accurate, and well-documented indicators for research activities, outputs, and impact.

Designed for research organisations, funders, and communities.
Tailored to advance Open Science.

Assess

OpenAIRE CONNECT – a customized (Re)search engine

How to customise your portal

Keywords: Discipline-specific subject terms to be found in the metadata

Projects: From the 85 funders integrated in OpenAIRE

Data Sources: from repositories and Zenodo communities, archives and journals

Organisations: Institutions repositories, CRIS, and Affiliations

Advanced Criteria: Combine criteria in AND or OR, like in an advanced search

EnerMaps Open Data Management Tool aims to **improve data management** and **accessibility** in the field of **energy research** for the **renewable energy industry**.

EnerMaps' tool accelerates and facilitates the energy transition offering a qualitative and user-friendly digital platform to the energy professionals.

The project is based on the **FAIR data principle** which requires data to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

EnerMaps project coordinates and enriches existing energy databases to promote **trans-disciplinary research** and to develop partnerships between researchers and the energy professionals.

The EnerMaps project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under [grant agreement N°884161](#).

Website: <https://enermaps.eu/>

Gateway Information

Curated by: [Jakob Rager](#) , [Argiro Kokogiannaki](#)

Created: 08-Jun-2020

1,702

Projects [?](#)

50

Linked Zenodo Communities [?](#)

127

Data sources [?](#)

678

Subjects

Publications

1.1M

Research data

49.9K

Research software

1K

Other research products

76.1K

Website: <https://enermaps.eu/>

Enemap – a case study

76.1K

Other research products

1.1M

Publications

49.9K

Research data

1K

Research software

Featured datasets

Here are listed some of the most important energy datasets as selected by energy experts.

Check them if you want to easily explore and visualize the European energy landscape, using only well-known datasets which you can trust.

1

2

3

4

5

>

EMHIRES: Wind power generation

 Research Data >> Dataset • 2019 • Publisher: Joint Research Centre

Authors: *Gonzalez Aparicio, Iratxe; Zucker, Andreas; Careri, Francesco; Monforti, Fabio*; **+2 Authors**

High resolution renewable energy generation time series data of wind power capacity factors at NUTS 2 level.

TABULA: Building typology

 Research Data >> Dataset

Authors: *TABULA project*

Building typology data

Enemap – a case study

OpenAIRE MONITOR

Tracking Research Practices

Open Science Indicators

Linked to funding data, classifications (FOS, SDGs), FAIR metrics, etc.

Supported by AI analysis to get more insights.

**Browse to the OpenAIRE Communitites
you like or ask one for you:**

<https://enermaps.openaire.eu/>
<https://energy-planning.openaire.eu/>
<https://lifewatch-eric.openaire.eu/>
<https://beopen.openaire.eu/>

Thanks for Listening

Email: giulia.malaguarnera@openaire.eu

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CUESTIONARIO DE GIULIA MALAGUARNERA

1 ¿What does the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” mean in Open Science?

- A) Research outputs should be made openly accessible whenever possible, but some data (e.g. personal, biomedical, security) may need restrictions.**
- B) All research outputs must always be fully open to everyone without exceptions.
- C) Open Science only applies to publications, not to data or software.

2 ¿Which of the following is a service provided by OpenAIRE to support Open Science?

- A) OpenAIRE Graph, which links publications, datasets, software, and projects across research domains.**
- B) A private journal ranking system for universities.
- C) A repository limited only to biomedical research.

3 ¿Why is there a gap between Open Science policies and their adoption by researchers?

- A) Because academic culture still rewards traditional publications more than open datasets or software.**
- B) Because Open Science is not recognized by the European Commission.
- C) Because researchers are not allowed to use OpenAIRE or EOSC platforms.

Open Science publication impact and methods of quality

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la Unión Europea

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Open Science

► **Open Science** is the practice of science in such a way that others can collaborate and contribute, where research data, lab notes and other research processes are freely available, under terms that enable reuse, redistribution and reproduction of the research and its underlying data and methods.

Open Science - taxonomy

- Open Access is the practice of providing unrestricted access via the Internet to peer-reviewed scholarly journal articles.
- Open Access is also increasingly being provided to theses, scholarly monographs and book chapters.

Creative Commons – Open Licenses

CREATIVE COMMONS LICENSES		CHANGE LICENSE				
	PUBLIC DOMAIN	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
	CC BY	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	CC BY-SA	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗
	CC BY-ND	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓
	CC BY-NC	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
	CC BY-NC-SA	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗
	CC BY-NC-ND	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓

You can redistribute (copy, publish, display, communicate, etc.)	You have to attribute the original work	You can use the work commercially	You can modify and adapt the original work	You can choose license type for your adaptations of the work.

UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science

<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949>

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EOSC European Open Science Cloud

- Mission: shift scholarly communication towards openness and transparency and facilitate innovative ways to communicate and monitor research
- Vision: Transform society through validated scientific knowledge, allow citizens, educators, funders, civil servants and industry find ways to make science useful for themselves, their working environments, the society.

European Commission OPEN SCIENCE

Eight ambitions:

- Open Data: FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable data)
- European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)
- New Generation Metrics
- Future of scholarly communication
- Rewards
- Research integrity
- Education and skills
- Citizen science

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/research_and_innovation/knowledge_publications_tools_and_data/documents/ec_rtd_factsheet-open-science_2019.pdf

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EOSC
European
Open
Science
Cloud

Activities:

- Align policies
- Provide Open Science services
- Link research
- Monitor Open Science
- Train for Open Science
- Build global bridges
- Facilitate Open Innovation

<https://www.openaire.eu/achieving-open-science-in-eosc>

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OPEN DATA

- ‘Open knowledge’ is any content, information or data that people are free to use, re-use and redistribute — without any legal, technological or social restriction.
- <https://okfn.org/opendata/>

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Open Science & Open Access in UPT

The screenshot shows the website for the UPT Library Institutional Digital Repository. The header includes navigation links like Home, Browse, and Help, along with a search bar and user options. The main banner features a colorful illustration of a modern building and the text 'UPT Library Institutional Digital Repository'. Below the banner, a paragraph describes the repository's offerings. The lower section is divided into three columns: 'Communities in DSpace' with a link to the central library, 'Discover' with a list of authors and their item counts, and a filter section for 'Subject', 'Date issued', and 'Has File(s)' with corresponding item counts.

Depozitul digital / The digital library BCUPT

UPT Library

Institutional Digital Repository

The Digital Repository of the Central Library of the Politehnica University of Timișoara offers to her users the institutional information resources: scientific articles, courses, PhD theses, etc. necessary to the information and documentation activities, also to the scientific research in technical field.

Communities in DSpace

Choose a community to browse its collections.

- Biblioteca Centrala a Universitatii Politehnica Timisoara

Discover

Author	Count
Buchman, Iosif	45
Oficiul de Stat pentru Invenții ș...	42
Negrea, Adina	28
Negrea, Petru	27
Badea, Cătălin	26
Kovács, Adalbert	26
Ionel, Ioana	23
Lupa, Lavinia Afrodita	23
Man, Eugen Teodor	23
Beilicci, Erika Beata Maria	22

next >

Subject	Count
Teză de doctorat	2139
Curs	534
Articol	303
Laborator	217
Probleme	137
Chimie organică	94
Rezistența materialelor	81
Proiectare complexă	72
Aplicații	66
Construcții	61

next >

Date issued	Count
2000 - 2024	4279
1900 - 1999	1337
1877 - 1899	1

Has File(s)	Count
true	5643

<https://dspace.upt.ro/jspui/>

Open Science & Open Access in UPT

dspace.upt.ro/jspui/handle/123456789/1118

Home Browse Help Search DSpace Sign on to: Language

Depozitul digital / The digital library BCUPT / Biblioteca Centrala a Universitatii Politehnica Timisoara / Articole stiintifice/Scientific articles

Please use this identifier to cite or link to this item: <https://dspace.upt.ro/xmlui/handle/123456789/1118>

DOI: null

Title: The MPEG-7 query of the e-learning content [articol]

Authors: VasIU, Radu Adrian
Gabor, Andrei Marius

Subjects: MPEG-7
Multimedia database
MP7QF framework
E-learning

Issue Date: 2011

Publisher: Editura Politehnica

Citation: Gabor, Andrei Marius. The MPEG-7 query of the e-learning content. Timișoara: Editura Politehnica, 2011

Series/Report no.: Seria electronică și telecomunicații; Tom 56(70), fasc. 2 (2011)

Abstract: Based on nowadays progress, the quantity of multimedia data that is stored has increased progressively during the e-learning platforms. The value of multimedia information depends on the easiness of having access to it, filtering and managing. Therefore, there is the necessity of organizing and accessing the content efficiently, in order to help its user. The proposed architecture uses MP7QF framework specific to MPEG-7 standard to query multiple database in order to create, distribute and consume the returned digital information, in the e-learning context.

URI: <http://localhost:8080/xmlui/handle/123456789/1118>

Appears in Collections: Articole stiintifice/Scientific articles

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File	Description	Size	Format
BUPT_ART_Vasiu_f.pdf		719.08 kB	Adobe PDF

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Title: Regenerarea și refuncționalizarea fostei gari "Buzias-Bai"

Authors: Anghel, Andreea
Vicol, Daniel

Subjects: Patrimoniu
Re-use
Sustenabilitate
Balnear
Gară
Industrie
Regenerare
Restaurare patrimonială
Regenerare patrimonială
Reconversie patrimonială

Issue Date: Jun-2022

Publisher: Universitatea Politehnica Timișoara, Facultatea Arhitectură și Urbanism, Departamentul Arhitectură

Citation: Anghel, Andreea; Vicol, Daniel. Regenerarea și refuncționalizarea fostei gari "Buzias-Bai". Timișoara: Universitatea Politehnica Timișoara, Facultatea Arhitectură și Urbanism, Departamentul Arhitectură, 2022.

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Title: Integrating linked open data in mobile augmented reality applications

Authors: Vert, Silviu

Subjects: Mediu virtual
Realitate augmentată
Turism
Teză de doctorat

Issue Date: 2015

Publisher: Timișoara: Editura Politehnica

Citation: Vert, Silviu. Integrating linked open data in mobile augmented reality applications. Timișoara: Editura Politehnica, 2015

Series/Report no.: 7 Inginerie Electronică și Telecomunicații;80

Abstract: Teza de față abordează aspecte actuale privind preluarea, prelucrarea și integrarea diverselor date deschise existente în acest moment pe World Wide Web. Datele obținute sunt destinate exploataării în aplicații mobile, create în scop turistic, ce folosesc tehnologii de realitate augmentată. Studiul critic al evoluției și stadiului actual al tehnologiilor de realitate augmentată, împreună cu analiza maturității principiilor și uneltelor de publicare și consum a datelor interconectate, au scos la iveală avantajele integrării datelor deschise interconectate în aplicații mobile de realitate augmentată pentru turism, dar și provocările ridicate de o astfel de integrare. Autorul propune un model și descrie implementarea unui prototip de aplicație mobilă, care integrează atât date deschise guvernamentale cât și date deschise generate de utilizatori și care folosește realitatea augmentată bazată pe tehnologii web pentru a ajuta un turist să descopere puncte de interes în jurul său. Este inclusă de asemenea și o analiză a profilului datelor integrate, împreună cu o comparație a aplicației dezvoltate cu alte aplicații similare.

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Title: Supermatematica Vol.1

Other Titles: Fundamente

Authors: Şelariu, Mircea Eugen

Subjects: Matematici speciale
Supermatematică

Issue Date: 2007

Publisher: Timișoara: Editura Politehnica

Citation: Şelariu, Mircea Eugen, 1938-. Supermatematica : Fundamente. Timișoara: Editura Politehnica, 2007

Series/Report no.: Matematici Moderne;Vol. 1

URI: <https://dspace.upt.ro/xmlui/handle/123456789/6108>

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Search Results:

- 1. CARTE Advances in **Multimedia** Information Processing, PCM 2012: 13th Pacific-Rim Conference on **Multimedia**, Singapore, December 4-6, 2012, Proceedings. PEER REVIEWED. Full text contra cost >
- 2. CARTE Advances in **Multimedia** Information Processing - PCM 2016: 17th Pacific-Rim Conference on **Multimedia**, Xi'an, China, September 15-16, 2016, Proceedings, Part I. PEER REVIEWED. Full text contra cost >
- 3. CARTE Advances in **Multimedia** Information Processing - PCM 2009: 10th Pacific Rim Conference on **Multimedia**, Bangkok, Thailand, December 15-18, 2009. Proceedings. PEER REVIEWED. Full text contra cost >
- 4. CARTE Interactive **Multimedia** and Next Generation Networks: Second International Workshop on **Multimedia** Interactive Protocols and Systems, MIPS 2004, Grenoble, France, November 16-19, 2004, Proceedings.

Filters:

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- Subiect: Computer Science (223.472), Science & Technology (205.408), Technology (165.993), Multimedia (121.717), Engineering (94.729), Arată mai mult

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The screenshot shows the UPT Primo search interface. The search bar contains the query 'vasiu'. The results page displays four articles, each with a document icon, title, journal information, and 'PEER REVIEWED' and 'OPEN ACCESS' badges. A sidebar on the right offers filters for 'Rafinarea rezultatelor', 'Sortare după', 'Disponibilitate', 'Tip resursă', and 'Subiect'. The top navigation bar includes links for 'CĂUTARE NOUĂ', 'ÎNTREABĂ BIBLIOTECARUL', and 'CONTUL PERSONAL DE BIBLIOTECĂ'. A yellow banner at the top of the results area encourages user identification for full results.

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Management of Sustainable Development, 2023-12, Vol.15 (2), p.80-86
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On Lie algebra modules which are modules over semisimple group schemes
Manuscripta mathematica, 2024, Vol.173 (3-4), p.1171-1193
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Disponibilitate

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Full text online (2)

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Articole (578)

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SCIENTIFIC BULLETIN OF THE POLITEHNICA UNIVERSITY OF TIMIȘOARA: TRANSACTIONS ON MODERN LANGUAGES (NOV 2022)

Dejica-Carțiș, Anca. 2020. Deutsch für den Beruf. Lehr-und Arbeitsbuch für Studierende der Studienrichtung: Kommunikation und PR. Timișoara: Politehnica Verlag. ISBN 978-606-35-0399-3.

Veronica CÂMPIAN

Journal subjects
Language and Literature: Philology. Linguistics: Language. Linguistic theory. Comparative grammar

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Open Science

Los Angeles Times: 3rd March 2020

“COVID-19 could kill the for-profit science publishing model. That would be a good thing.”

- Coronavirus demonstrates the value of open access to scientific research.
- Unprecedented level of collaboration among researchers worldwide: this virtually real-time sharing is the exception in scientific research, not the rule.
- PubMed: free database of research papers maintained by the National Institutes of Health in the USA, growing daily.
- But: Among the major violators of the principle that a crisis demands more information, not less, is the U.S. government.

The longstanding research publication model doesn't work when a critical need arises for rapid dissemination of data — like now.

<https://www.latimes.com/business/story/2020-03-03/covid-19-open-science>

- The critics support an “open access” model, through which research grant institutions pay fees for publication, but require that their funded research be made accessible without charge.
- **Elsevier, Springer and other commercial publishers have temporarily dropped their paywalls** on coronavirus-related research, but they say the action is limited to the duration of the crisis and doesn't apply to other published research.
- “The responsible thing to do is to make all research freely available during epidemics or possibly pandemics where there are people at risk,” Edward Campion, executive editor of the New England Journal of Medicine

Open Science

- ▶ Among the leaders in the open-access movement is the **University of California**, which ended its subscriptions to about 2,500 Elsevier journals after it failed to come to terms with the publisher on liberating access to UC research.
- ▶ The university proposed that its annual subscription bill of about \$11 million cover not only access to the Elsevier journals but publication fees for articles that would be made freely available. Elsevier balked, and shut off UC's access to the journals in July 2019.
- ▶ **Research consortiums in Germany and Sweden** have dropped their subscriptions to Elsevier, though the publisher has been able to work out compromises in other countries, including Italy and the Netherlands.

- ▶ “The scientific literature is controlled by largely commercial journals” says Randy Schekman, a Nobellaureate biologist at UC Berkeley who founded Elife, a non-profit open access publisher, in 2011 with support from the Howard Hughes Medical Institute and other backers. **“Decisions are made by professional editors who are in the business of selling magazines,** which make a huge profit by virtue of controlling copyright on the literature and by controlling access to the literature.”

Albuiescu Claudiu Tiberiu

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Banks' profitability and financial soundness indicators: A macro-level investigation in emerging countries CT Albuiescu Procedia economics and finance 23, 203-209	180	2015
Forecasting the Romanian financial system stability using a stochastic simulation model CT Albuiescu romanian journal of economic Forecasting 13 (1), 81-98	163	2010
Does the US economic policy uncertainty connect financial markets? Evidence from oil and commodity currencies CT Albuiescu, R Demirel, ID Raheem, AK Tiwari Energy Economics 83, 375-388	134	2019
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Do foreign direct and portfolio investments affect long-term economic growth in Central and Eastern Europe? CT Albuiescu Procedia economics and finance 23, 507-512	100	2015
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Impact of corporate social responsibility practices on the banking industry in Romania M Mocan, S Rus, A Draghici, L Ivascu, A Turi Procedia Economics and Finance 23, 712-716	101	2015
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Martin Hagve About the author

The academic publishing industry earns high profits and shapes how we undertake medical research. With the increasing demand for free access to articles, academic publishing is now changing, but is it changing for the better?

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Published: 17 August 2020

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Darren Chase | darren.chase@stonybrook.edu | Stony Brook University | Libraries

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- Depositing full texts of publications in repositories requires extra effort to comply with Open Access policies of research funders..
- Not all Open Access journals are covered in the Open Access agreements between universities and publishers. As such, you may need to pay for publishing via the Gold Open Access route. High APC for good journals / high impact journals
- Predatory journals:** the Open Access business model, where the author pays, is potentially an invitation for dubious publishers to accept more papers and provide less stringent review. This could lead to higher costs and a negative impact on overall quality.
- Artificial increase of Impact Factors for some journals by citations recommendations.
- Practices to recommend other OA journals from the same Editor when papers are rejected.

Open Access

Total number of articles

For 2011 - 2021 period

Elsevier ↑ 2 times

Springer ↑ 1.6 times

MDPI ↑ 51 times !!!

Scientometrics

Table 1 Retrospective statistics of the leading academic publishers in 2021, and the changes in the number of SCI/SSCI articles they published

	Number of articles published in 2021	Number of articles published in 2016	Number of articles published in 2011	Change from 2016 to 2021 (%)	Change from 2011 to 2016 (%)
Elsevier	600,623	394,898	313,818	152.10	125.84
Springer Nature	319,122	261,583	196,535	122.00	133.10
MDPI	211,333	19,471	4076	1085.37	477.70
Wiley	189,813	148,008	136,489	128.25	108.44
Taylor & Francis	102,950	90,968	72,420	113.17	125.61
Frontiers Media	73,927	12,675	1896	540.60	721.26
Sa					
IEEE	69,483	34,453	25,139	201.67	137.05
Amer Chemical Soc	60,733	42,387	36,986	143.28	114.60
Sage	56,271	40,702	32,422	138.25	125.54
Oxford Univ Press	55,833	39,377	35,077	141.79	112.26
Royal Soc Chemistry	39,177	42,321	20,557	92.57	205.87
Lippincott Williams & Wilkins	34,307	31,614	28,569	108.52	110.66
Iop Publishing Ltd	26,338	24,009	22,699	109.70	105.77
Public Library Science	19,797	25,218	16,005	78.50	157.56
Cambridge Univ Press	19,576	18,485	13,270	105.90	139.30
Amer Physical Soc	19,422	18,342	18,973	105.89	96.67
Hindawi	18,805	12,132	4434	155.00	273.61
Bmj Publishing Group	13,507	6575	4681	205.43	140.46
Walter De Gruyter	9980	10,663	8179	93.59	130.37
Optical Soc Amer	8624	7946	7107	108.53	111.81
Amer Geophysical Union	8073	6207	5120	130.06	121.23
World Scientific	7260	6678	5250	108.72	127.20
Thieme Medical Publishers	6423	6225	5818	103.18	107.00
Mary Ann Liebert, Inc	5793	5353	6158	108.22	86.93
Science Press	5399	5069	6446	106.51	78.64
Karger	5202	5271	6000	98.69	87.85

Data have been derived from Clarivate's InCites Benchmarking and Analytics platform

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G. Csomós, J. Z. Farkas, Understanding the increasing market share of the academic publisher “Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute” in the publication output of Central and Eastern European countries: a case study of Hungary, Scientometrics, 2022.

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Publication time

Share of articles by turnaround time classes per leading academic publishers

Lack of quality control

	within 1 month	1 month - 3 months	4 months - 6 months	7 months - 12 months	over 12 months
Subscription-based publishers*	0.85	22.67	40.66	28.10	7.72
MDPI	30.55	67.06	2.39	0.00	0.00
Frontiers	0.00	28.62	55.80	13.41	2.17
IEEE ACCESS	57.14	42.86	0.00	0.00	0.00
PLOS ONE	0.00	16.22	54.05	29.73	0.00
Scientific Reports	0.51	10.77	54.87	32.82	1.03

Data in percentage

*Elsevier, Springer Nature, Wiley, Taylor & Francis, Oxford University Press

G. Csomós, J. Z. Farkas, Understanding the increasing market share of the academic publisher “Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute” in the publication output of Central and Eastern European countries: a case study of Hungary, *Scientometrics*, 2022.

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Case study: MDPI

Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute

Number of articles

Universitatea
de Tehnica
Cluj-Napoca

Open Access

Case study : MDPI

Number of *Special Issues*

2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021*
388	475	710	990	1386	2342	4096	6756	39587

Number of Special Issues at 74 MDPI journals with an IF.

*open special issues with a closing date in 2021

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Publications indexed in Web of Science Core Collection (Romania, 2022, articles & reviews, ISI journals publishers-top 25)

Fees for Romania

**5584 articles x 2000 Eur (APC) =
11.168.000 Eur !**

Publishers	Publications	% of 13,010
Mdpi	5584	42.92
Elsevier	1521	11.69
Springer Nature	1142	8.78
Taylor & Francis	508	3.91
Wiley	466	3.58
Frontiers Media Sa	385	2.96
Editura Acad Romane	198	1.52
NATURE PORTFOLIO	158	1.21
Spandidos Publ Ltd	156	1.20
Sage	149	1.15
Amer Physical Soc	128	0.98
Oxford Univ Press	116	0.89
IEEE	107	0.82
Iop Publishing Ltd	85	0.65
Amer Inst Mathematical Sciences- Aims	83	0.64
Soc Stiinte Farmaceutice Romania	75	0.58
Lippincott Williams & Wilkins	67	0.52
Amer Chemical Soc	62	0.48
Emerald Group Publishing	62	0.48
Hindawi Publishing Group	60	0.46
Royal Soc Chemistry	57	0.44
Cambridge Univ Press	54	0.42
Dove Medical Press Ltd	53	0.41
Editura Ase	50	0.38
Bmj Publishing Group	45	0.35

Open Access

Case study : MDPI

Number of *corresponding authors*

Open Access Article

Physical and Chemical Properties of Vegetable Films Based on Pumpkin Purée and Biopolymers of Plant and Animal Origin

by ,

¹ Department of Food Engineering and Process Management, Institute of Food Sciences, Warsaw University of Life Sciences—SGGW, 159c Nowoursynowska St., 02-776 Warsaw, Poland

² Division of Organic and Food Chemistry, Department of Chemistry, Institute of Food Sciences, Warsaw University of Life Sciences—SGGW, 159c Nowoursynowska St., 02-776 Warsaw, Poland

* Authors to whom correspondence should be addressed.

Molecules **2023**, *28*(12), 4626; <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28124626> (registering DOI)

Received: 10 May 2023 / Revised: 3 June 2023 / Accepted: 6 June 2023 / Published: 7 June 2023

(This article belongs to the Special Issue **Edible Films and Coatings from Fruits or Vegetables**)

Open Access

Excluded journals by Web of Science (2023)

<https://predatoryreports.org/news/f/web-of-science-de-listed-82-journal-including-15-from-hindawi>

Publisher	De-listed	Core Collection	%
Hindawi LTD	15	163	9,2%
Routledge Journals, Taylor & Francis LTD	4	1187	0,3%
Wiley-Hindawi	4	26	15,4%
AME Publishing Company	2	18	11,1%
BMJ Publishing Group	2	59	3,4%
MDPI	2	207	1,0%
Sage Publications LTD	2	428	0,5%
Springer	2	1060	0,2%
Springer Heidelberg	2	301	0,7%
Wiley	2	1356	0,1%

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Other Journals considered predatory listed by Jeffery Beall

<https://beallist.net/>

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Causes

Individual

- Requirements based exclusively on scientometric criterias for promotion!
- Support from universities for covering the APC, participation in conferences, rewards in salary for researchers
- Grants for publications in Q1 and Q2 journals by UEFISCDI

- Requirement for Open Access publishing for dissemination of national, European projects
- Consideration of scientometric criteria in research evaluation and financing of universities

Institutional

Prof.em.dr.eng. Radu VasIU

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CUESTIONARIO DE RADU VASIU

1 What is the main difference between Gold Open Access and Green Open Access publishing models?

A) Gold provides immediate open access often with author fees, while Green allows depositing a version in an open repository

B) Gold applies only to EU-funded projects, while Green applies worldwide

C) Gold is limited to conference papers, while Green is for journal articles

D) Gold requires publishing in a subscription-based journal, while Green involves paying publication fees

2 How can Open Access publishing increase researchers' visibility and impact?

A) By improving scientometric indicators such as h-index in WoS, Scopus, or Google Scholar

B) By restricting access to research outputs

C) By preventing research from being cited widely

D) By reducing compliance with EU and UNESCO recommendations

3 Which of the following best describes the role of Creative Commons (CC) licenses in Open Access publishing?

A) They provide standardized open licenses that define how research outputs can be reused and shared

B) They ensure research is only accessible within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

C) They restrict the distribution of research to subscription-only journals

D) They replace peer review in the publishing process

Open Science Tools

Dr. eng. Diana ANDONE

Director Digital and Distance Education Department
Politehnica University of Timisoara, Romania

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Biotic interactions, community assembly, and eco-evolutionary dynamics as drivers of long-term biodiversity–ecosystem functioning relationships

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Abstract ▲

The functioning and service provisioning of ecosystems in the face of anthropogenic environmental and biodiversity change is a cornerstone of ecological research. The last three decades of biodiversity–ecosystem functioning (BEF) research have provided compelling evidence for the significant positive role of biodiversity in the functioning of many ecosystems. Despite broad consensus of this relationship, the underlying ecological and evolutionary mechanisms have not been well understood. This complicates the transition from a description of patterns to a predictive science. The proposed Research

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Scientific equipment

Coordinating the Research Unit also means to provide all scientist with reliable data on plot-specific soil properties and site specific meteorological data. Therefore, a main *meteorological station* as well as a *CanBus system* were installed in 2002, and in the past, these data have been shown to be of central relevance for long-term times-series analyses within and syntheses beyond the Jena Experiment. After 17 years of operation, the technical equipment has to renewed and needs regular maintenance. The maintenance itself will be done by a technician from the central project.

Weather Station Maintenance (EUR 2,500.00 per year): EUR 10,000.00

CanBus System Renewal: EUR 9,110.33

CanBus Maintenance (EUR 2,400.00 per year): EUR 9,600.00

Total sum of requested funds in 'Scientific equipment': EUR 28,710.33

Overall budget and requested personnel

Total sum of requested funds in the Coordination Proposal: 300.060,00 €

Total sum of requested funds in the Research Unit: 5,317,500 €

Requested number of PhD positions: 11 (65%)

Requested number of postdocs: 1 (100%)

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Overall budget and requested personnel

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Total sum of requested funds in the Research Unit: 5,317,500 €

Requested number of PhD positions: 11 (65%)

Requested number of postdocs: 1 (100%)

Requested number of data curators: 1 (50%)

Requested number of technicians: 4

Acknowledgements ▲

We thank the eight reviewers for their very helpful feedback on our research plan and the positive evaluation. We thank the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG; German Research Foundation) for financial support (FOR 456, FOR 1451, FOR 5000) as well as the Friedrich-Schiller-University Jena, Max-Planck-Institute for Biogeochemistry Jena, Leipzig University, and the German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv) Halle-Jena-Leipzig, funded by the German Research Foundation (FZT 118), for financial and logistical help with the set-up and maintenance of the Jena Experiment. We also thank the gardeners for their great help maintaining the experimental plots and Ernst-Detlef Schulze for initiating the Jena Experiment. Moreover, we thank Anja Vogel for coordinating the setup of the Field Experiment, as well as Kathrin G. and Christian H. for their help with the data management.

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Supplementary materials ▲

Suppl. material 1: Design of the Field Experiment [doi](#)

Authors: Eisenhauer et al.

Data type: Text

Brief description: Detailed design of the Field Experiment

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Suppl. material 2: Cheat sheet Field Experiment [doi](#)

Authors: Eisenhauer et al.

Data type: Text

Brief description: Brief description of the Field Experiment

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Suppl. material 3: Plant species list [doi](#)

Authors: Eisenhauer et al.

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Abstract

The functioning and service provisioning of ecosystems in the face of anthropogenic environmental and biodiversity change is a cornerstone of ecological research. The last three decades of biodiversity–ecosystem functioning (BEF) research have provided compelling evidence for the significant positive role of biodiversity in the functioning of many ecosystems. Despite broad consensus of this relationship, the underlying ecological and evolutionary mechanisms have not been well understood. This complicates the transition from a description of patterns to a predictive science. The proposed Research

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Francisco Hita Garcia

03:18 on 3 Nov. 2013

Citation: Hita Garcia F (2013) Review of: Biotic interactions, community assembly, and eco-evolutionary dynamics as drivers of long-term biodiversity–ecosystem functioning relationships. Research Ideas and Outcomes 5: e47042. doi: [10.3897/rio.5.e47042.r3327](https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.5.e47042.r3327)

Notes

Dear Dr. Varga,
 thank you for submitting your manuscript "A review of the subfamily Acaenitinae Förster, 1869 (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae) from Ukrainian Carpathians" for review to Biodiversity Data Journal.

After consideration of the opinion of two nominated reviewers and one panel reviewer, we think your manuscript may be acceptable for publication pending major revision. Two of the reviewers have a number of major concerns, points of critique and suggestions, and in the main I agree with most them. Please, read through the comments and suggestions of the reviewers and try to modify your manuscript accordingly. Of special importance is the use of English grammar. Please, as suggested, let someone with good English skills

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The making of a (dog) movie star: The effect of the portrayal of dogs in movies on breed registrations in the United States

Language en

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Abstract The media is a powerful forc... >

1 Attachment + >

PLOS ONE

RESEARCH ARTICLE

The making of a (dog) movie star: The effect of the portrayal of dogs in movies on breed registrations in the United States

Sarah Weir ^{1*}, Sharon E. Kessler
Department of Psychology, Faculty of Natural Sciences, University of Stirling, Stirling, Scotland, United Kingdom
 * s.a.weir@stirling.ac.uk

Abstract

The media is a powerful force that can affect the welfare of the domestic dog population. Dogs have long been in human stories and their depictions can create demand for the breeds shown. While previous research has found that this effect can last for up to ten years after the release of a movie, how this phenomenon occurs is unclear. This paper examines if how a dog is portrayed in a movie is associated with a subsequent change in American Kennel Club breed registrations for that breed. Following a systematic literature review, four key themes were identified in how dogs are portrayed in the media: dogs portrayed as heroes, as anthropomorphised, as embodying the ideals of Western societies (whiteness and heteronormativity) and as boundaries between wilderness and human society. Forty studies from between 1980 to 2024 were analysed, resulting in 95 dog characters scored, and 10 historical multiple linear regression was run. Movies with dogs portrayed as heroes were followed by significant increases in the number of American Kennel Club breed registrations for the breed shown, while anthropomorphised dogs were followed by significant decreases in the number of dogs registered for up to five years after a movie's release. These results indicate that how dogs are portrayed may be an important driver of demand for breeds. Future work should investigate whether these portrayals may have negative well-being implications for real dogs by leading to owners having unrealistic expectations for dogs or increasing demand for dogs with in-breeding related disorders.

Introduction

Dogs have been used in human stories for centuries, usually to reflect human lives and emotions [1]. A recent iteration of these stories is told through movies, and dogs have been critical

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For the measurement of cortical protein association, immunostaining of the cortical regulator under consideration was combined with fluorescent DNA staining (DAPI or Hoechst) which allowed to identify cells to be in an interphase or mitotic stage, see Materials and Methods. For the measurement of cortical regulators in mitotic cells, the fraction of mitotic cells was enriched through mitotic arrest induced by co-incubation with S-trityl-L-cysteine (STC), see Materials and Methods. Using a previously established image analysis scheme, we analysed confocal images of immunostaining fluorescence intensities to infer the cellular outline and the averaged cortical fluorescence profile along the radial coordinate, i.e. orthogonal to the cell boundary, see Fig. 1b and [5, 18]. The averaged radial fluorescence intensity was then used to derive the cortex-to-cytoplasm ratio of protein localization in the cells by calculating the ratio of the integrated cortical fluorescence normalized by the cytoplasmic fluorescence intensity, see Fig. 1c and Materials and Methods and [5, 18].

2.1. Rho GTPases change their cortical association upon EMT in a cell-cycle-dependent manner

To investigate whether cortical association of Rho GTPases changes through EMT, we quantified the cortex-to-cytoplasm ratio of RhoA, RhoC and Rac1 in cells with and without EMT induction. To this end, we performed confocal imaging of the equatorial cross section of suspended interphase or STC-arrested mitotic cells which were immunostained for either of the Rho GTPases under consideration, see Fig. 1d and Materials and Methods. Quantitative analysis shows that the cortex-to-cytoplasm ratio of Rac1 increases upon EMT both in interphase and mitosis (Fig. 1d,e). By contrast, the cortex-to-cytoplasm ratio of RhoA decreases through EMT (Fig. 1d,f). We conclude that cortical association of Rac1 and RhoA follows the EMT-induced quantitative change of GTP-bound Rac1 and RhoA in whole-cell-lysates of MCF-7 cells [5]. The cortex-to-cytoplasm ratio of RhoC changes in a cell-cycle-dependent manner upon EMT. While cortical RhoC goes down in interphase, we see an increase of cortical RhoC in mitosis (Fig. 1d,g). Our results on the effect of EMT on cortical signalling of Rho GTPases is summarized in Fig. 1h.

We further asked about the influence of Rho GTPases on cortical mechanics. For this purpose, we relied on cortex-mechanical measurements with an established cell confinement setup based on oscillatory cell-squishing with the cantilever of an atomic force microscope (AFM). We chose a deformation frequency of 1 Hz. This assay was previously shown to provide a readout of cortical stiffness, cortical tension as well as a characterization of the viscoelastic nature of the

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Dr. Wickramasinghe 3 hrs ago

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2.1. Rho GTPases change their cortical association upon EMT in a cell-cycle-dependent manner

This finding could have several interesting implications:

- 1. Rho GTPases and EMT:** As Rho GTPases are involved in cell migration and polarity, their altered cortical association could impact the EMT process. This might result in changes to cell morphology, migratory capacity, and other aspects of cell behavior during EMT.
- 2. Cell Cycle Dependence:** If this process is cell-cycle-dependent, it indicates a complex regulation of cell behavior in which the status of the cell (e.g., which phase of the cell cycle it is in) can dictate Rho GTPase activity and consequently, the EMT process. This complexity could contribute to how a cell decides when to undergo EMT, which could have profound implications for both physiological and pathological situations.
- 3. Clinical Implications:** Understanding this process could have significant implications for disease treatment, particularly in cancer. If the cortical association of Rho GTPases is necessary for cancer cells to undergo EMT and metastasize, then disrupting this association could be a potential therapeutic strategy to halt cancer progression.

arXiv:1611.04558v2 [cs.CL] 21 Aug 2017

Google's Multilingual Neural Machine Translation Enabling Zero-Shot Translation

Melvin Johnson, Mike Schuster, Quoc V. Le, Maxim Krikun, Yonghui
Zhifeng Chen, Nikhil Thorat
melvinp,schuster,qvl,krikun,yonghui,zhifengc,nsthorat@
Fernanda Viégas, Martin Wattenberg, Greg Corrado
Macduff Hughes, Jeffrey Dean

Abstract

We propose a simple solution to use a single Neural Machine Translation (NMT) model between multiple languages. Our solution requires no changes to the model architecture but instead introduces an artificial token at the beginning of the input sentence to indicate the required target language. The rest of the model, which includes an encoder, decoder module, remains unchanged and is shared across all languages. Using a shared wordpiece approach enables Multilingual NMT using a single model without any increase in parameters. Our approach is significantly simpler than previous proposals for Multilingual NMT. On the WMT'14 benchmark, a single multilingual model achieves comparable performance for English→French and surpasses state-of-the-art results for English→German. Similarly, a single multilingual model surpasses state-of-the-art results for French→English and German→English on WMT'14 and WMT'15 benchmarks, respectively. On production corpora, multilingual models of up to twelve language pairs allow for better translation of many individual pairs. In addition to improving the translation quality of language pairs that the model was trained with, our models can also learn to perform implicit bridging between language pairs never seen explicitly during training, showing that transfer learning and zero-shot translation is possible for neural translation. Finally, we show analyses that hints at a universal interlingua representation in our models and show some interesting examples when mixing languages.

1 Introduction

End-to-end Neural Machine Translation (NMT) [27, 2, 5] is an approach to machine translation that has rapidly gained adoption in many large-scale settings [31, 29, 6]. Almost all such systems are built for a single language pair — so far there has not been a sufficiently simple and efficient way to handle multiple language pairs using a single model without making significant changes to the basic NMT architecture.

In this paper we introduce a simple method to translate between multiple languages using a single model, taking advantage of multilingual data to improve NMT for all languages involved. Our method requires no change to the traditional NMT model architecture. Instead, we add an artificial token to the input sequence to indicate the required target language, a simple amendment to the data only. All other parts of the system — encoder, decoder, attention, and shared wordpiece vocabulary as described in [29] — stay exactly the same. This method has several attractive benefits:

- **Simplicity:** Since no changes are made to the architecture of the model, scaling to more languages is trivial — any new data is simply added, possibly with over- or under-sampling such that all languages are appropriately represented, and used with a new token if the target language changes. Since no changes are made to the training procedure, the mini-batches for training are just sampled from the overall mixed-language training data just like for the single-language case. Since no a-priori decisions about how to allocate parameters for different languages are made the system adapts automatically to use the total number of parameters efficiently to minimize the global loss. A multilingual model architecture of this type also simplifies production deployment significantly since it can cut down the

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Rabah May 29, 2023
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Abstract

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used the annotation tool to note minor errors and to flag up other papers that agree or disagree with conclusions. And editorial staff have used it to contribute to the dialogue. In the 15 months since eLife introduced the system, more than 6,000 annotations have been posted on nearly 2,000 documents, although about half of those were made by eLife's automated curation assistant, SciBot.

"I don't think the quality of the dialogue in [the previous commenting system] was ever as constructive or as good as it is within the Hypothesis ecosystem," says Giuliano Maciocci, head of product and user experience at eLife in Cambridge, UK. That, he says, is probably because annotations are positioned on top or next to the text to which they refer, instead of at the bottom of the page as they are in conventional commenting systems.

Some publishers have integrated annotations into their peer-review processes. In the American Geophysical Union's system, for instance, comments can be organized by reviewer or editor, and by importance. Reviewers can see only their own comments, whereas editors can see all comments from reviewers and manuscript authors.

And some publishers are taking advantage of the tool's enhanced group feature, which allows users to create groups that are open (available to all users), private (anyone can read, but only invited members can annotate) or restricted (only invited members can see or add annotations). Last December, the American Society of Plant Biologists launched an open group for annotations on its journal Plant Cell; it has logged almost 30 comments.

Hypothesis is accessed using a Chrome extension, a bookmarklet, or the via.hypothes.is proxy server. In February 2017, the World Wide Web Consortium, or W3C, the international standards body for the web, formally recommended a web-annotation standard that allows developers to make annotation a native feature of their browsers. So far, none has done so.

Nature 569, 295 (2019)

doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-01427-9>

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How the similarity/diversity of the examples mentioned of a target event influences the probability people assign to that event. We expect that mentioning diverse examples of a target event would result in an overall higher probability judgment than mentioning similar examples of the target event.

3) Describe the key dependent variable(s) specifying how they will be measured.

The key dependent variable is probability judgment (How likely is it that [different text depending on condition]?, 0% = Not at all likely to 100% = Extremely likely). Other dependent variables include: the ease with which participants can imagine examples of the target event (How easy was it for you to think about [different text depending on condition]?, 1 = Not at all easy to 7 = Extremely easy), the number of examples of the target event they generate (time limit: 45 s), the number of different types of examples they generate, and a judgment of the

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No, no data have been collected for this study yet.

2) What's the main question being asked or hypothesis being tested in this study?

How do different styles of dynamically AI-generated learning examples, based on users' inputs (i.e., a prompted AI-generated sentence/story), influence their learning performance as assessed using quizzes (i.e., immediate/delayed quiz answers) and their subjective perception and attitude towards the overall learning experience (i.e. Interest/Enjoyment, Effort/Importance, Perceived Competence, Perceived Choice, Value/Usefulness) in an English vocabulary learning task, compared to static (i.e., non-AI-generated) learning examples?

3) Describe the key dependent variable(s) specifying how they will be measured.

Our key dependent variables are: (1) Immediate Vocabulary Quiz Answer (0-incorrect, 1-correct), (2) Delayed Vocabulary Quiz Answer (0-incorrect, 1-correct) (3) Interest/Enjoyment, (4) Effort/Importance, (5) Perceived Competence, (6) Perceived Choice, and (7) Value/Usefulness. Participants will complete the same vocabulary quiz twice, immediately after

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Stijn Peeters ; Sal Hagen ; Dale Wahl

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One year of ABHD2 – Where are we now?

📅 2nd October 2023 👤 Oliver Arnolds 💬 [Leave a comment](#)

The Recap

It's been one year since the last update on the α/β hydrolase domain 2 (ABHD2) as a target for non-hormonal contraception (see my previous post [here](#)). The major challenges were the production of ABHD2 and development of a reliable activity assay to screen and quantify inhibitory compounds. At that point 14 different constructs had been tested in *E. coli* and 17 in BEVS, both displaying only mediocre amounts of soluble protein either in the initial screen or after scale-up that were not sufficient for the use in downstream applications. In the meantime, other ABHDs (ABHD10, 11, and 14B) were purified with the aim to develop a selectivity panel as well as an activity assay using *p*-nitrophenyls as general hydrolase substrates.

The goal of this project is two-fold: Characterization of ABHD2 to evaluate the protein as a target for non-hormonal contraception as well as the generation of a full target-enabling package (TEP) that offers molecular tools for further investigation of the enzyme. This includes protocols for production of soluble ABHD2, assays that test folding status and activity of the purified protein, investigation of the effect of progesterone as well as the published inhibitor

Recent Posts

- [Co-expression and purification of recombinant hOvastacin and hFetuin B in insect cell sf9](#)
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Jan 07, 2025

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🌐 Inhibitor removal from DNA extracts

DOI

dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.rm7vzbp54vx1/v1

Dominik Buchner¹, Marie Borowski¹

¹University of Duisburg-Essen, Aquatic Ecosystem Research

Aquatic Ecosystem Rese...

Dominik Buchner

University of Duisburg-Essen, Aquatic Ecosystem Research

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Steps Guidelines Metadata Materials Metrics

Abstract

This protocol describes how to remove inhibitory substances such as humic substances from DNA that has already been extracted. The protocol is formulated for an initial input of 100 μL of extracted DNA however it can be adjusted to any other volume as well with minor changes. A lot of the buffers can be found in the following patent <https://patents.google.com/patent/US7459548B2/en>

Before starting

Inhibitor removal from DNA extracts

31m

- 1 Prepare 100 μL of sample in 2 mL tubes.

Sample contaminated with inhibitory substance (e.g. humic acids)

Note

This protocol is designed for a sample volume of 100 μL . Differing volumes can be used, however, all the following volumes have to be adjusted accordingly. For volumes smaller than 100 μL we recommend to simply fill up the sample to 100 μL with water and then proceed with the protocol. If a sample volume of 200 μL is to be processed, all volumes have to be doubled.

- 2 Add 345 μL bead-beating solution and 60 μL lysis solution .

10m

[Steps](#) [Guidelines](#) [Metadata](#) [Materials](#) [Metrics](#)

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Inhibitor removal from DNA extracts

31m

2 Add 345 μL bead-beating solution and 60 μL lysis solution .
Vortex shortly.

3 10000 x g, 20°C , 00:03:00 . Transfer all of the supernatant to a new tube.

Try to avoid the the pellet if any is formed.

4 Add 125 μL ammonium acetat buffer , vortex shortly and incubate at 4 °C for 00:05:00 .

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Add Equation

The beauty of mathematical formulations

MATHEMATICS QUANTUM MECHANICS

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Euler's identity is often cited as an example of deep mathematical beauty. It reads $e^{i\pi} + 1 = 0$

It merges in one beautiful relation all the most important numbers of mathematics. Stanford University mathematics professor Keith Devlin has said, "like a Shakespearean sonnet that captures the very essence of love, or a painting that brings out the beauty of the human form that is far more than just skin deep, Euler's equation reaches down into the very depths of existence". The beauty of mathematical formulations lies in abstracting, in simple equations, truths that have universal validity. Many have written of the experience of mathematical beauty as being comparable to that derived from the greatest art [\(Zeki 2014\)](#)

References

Semir Zeki, John Paul Romaya, Dionigi M. T. Benincasa, Michael F. Atiyah. The experience of mathematical beauty and its neural correlates. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience* 8 (2014). [Link](#)

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algorithms_in_ipython_notebooks / ipython_nbs / essentials

In [1]: `%load_ext watermark`In [2]: `%watermark -a 'Sebastian Raschka' -u -d -v`Sebastian Raschka
last updated: 2016-06-08CPython 3.5.1
IPython 4.2.0

Introduction to Greedy Algorithms

The subfamily of *Greedy Algorithms* is one of the main paradigms of algorithmic problem solving next to *Dynamic Programming* and *Divide & Conquer Algorithms*. The main goal behind greedy algorithms is to implement an efficient procedure for often computationally more complex, often infeasible brute-force methods such as exhaustive search algorithms.

The main outline of a greedy algorithms consists of 3 steps:

- make a greedy choice
- reduce the problem to a subproblem (a smaller problem of the similar type as the original one)
- repeat

So, greedy algorithms are essentially a problem solving heuristic, an iterative process of tackling a problem in multiple stages while making

Example 1: Coin Changer

To look at a first, naive example of a greedy algorithm, let's implement a simple coin changing machine. Given a money value in cents, we want to return the minimum possible number of coins, whereas the possible denominations are 1, 5, 10, and 20 cents.

```
In [3]: def coinchanger(cents, denominations=[1, 5, 10, 20]):
        coins = {d: 0 for d in denominations}
        for c in sorted(coins.keys(), reverse=True):
            coins[c] += cents // c
            cents = cents % c
        if not cents:
            total_coins = sum([i for i in coins.values()])
            return sorted(coins.items(), reverse=True), total_coins
```

The function above creates a dictionary, `coins`, which tracks the number of coins of each denomination to be returned. Then, we iterate through the denominations in descending order of their value. Now, in a "greedy" fashion, we count the highest possible number of coins from the largest denomination in the first step. We repeat this process until we reached the smallest denomination or the number of remaining `cents` reaches 0.

```
In [4]: coinchanger(cents=100)
```

```
Out[4]: ((20, 5), (10, 0), (5, 0), (1, 0)), 5)
```

Calling out `coinchanger` function with 100 cents as input, it returns 5 coins a 20 cents, the smallest, possible number of coins that can be returned in this case. Below are some more examples:

```
In [5]: coinchanger(cents=5)
```

```
Out[5]: ((20, 0), (10, 0), (5, 1), (1, 0)), 1)
```


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High Energy Physics - Experiment

[Submitted on 2 Jun 2025]

Search for Higgs boson decay to a charm quark-antiquark pair via $t\bar{t}H$ production

Sebastian Wuchterl (on behalf of the CMS Collaboration)

In these proceedings, a search for the standard model Higgs boson decaying to a charm quark-antiquark pair, $H \rightarrow c\bar{c}$, produced in association with a top quark-antiquark pair ($t\bar{t}H$) is presented. The search is performed using proton-proton collision data collected by the CMS experiment at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV, corresponding to an integrated luminosity of 138 fb^{-1} . The Higgs boson decay to a bottom quark-antiquark pair is measured simultaneously and the observed $t\bar{t}H(H \rightarrow bb)$ event rate relative to the standard model expectation is found to be $0.91^{+0.26}_{-0.22}$. The observed (expected) upper limit at 95% confidence level (CL) for $t\bar{t}H(H \rightarrow cc)$ production is 7.8 (8.7) times the standard model prediction. Combined with a previous search for $H \rightarrow c\bar{c}$ via associated production with a W or Z boson, the observed (expected) 95% CL interval on the Higgs-charm Yukawa coupling modifier, κ_c , is $\kappa_c < 3.5$ ($\kappa_c < 2.7$).

Comments: Contribution to the 59th Rencontres de Moriond on QCD & High Energy Interactions, La Thuile, Italy, 30 Mar - 6 Apr, 2025

Subjects: **High Energy Physics - Experiment (hep-ex)**

Report number: CMS-CR-2025-121

Cite as: arXiv:2506.02163 [hep-ex]

(or arXiv:2506.02163v1 [hep-ex] for this version)

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2506.02163>

Submission history

From: Sebastian Wuchterl [\[view email\]](#)

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Deep phenotyping of post-infectious myalgic encephalomyelitis/chronic fatigue syndrome

Brian Walitt, Komudi Singh, Samuel R. LaMunion, Mark Hallett, Steve Jacobson, Kong Chen, Yoshimi Enose-Akahata, Richard Apps, Jennifer J. Barb, Patrick Bedard, Robert J. Brychta, Ashura Williams Buckley, Peter D. Burbelo, Brice Calco, Brianna Cathay, Li Chen, Snigdha Chigurupati, Jinguo Chen, Foo Cheung, Lisa M. K. Chin, Benjamin W. Coleman, Amber B. Courville, Madeleine S. Deming, Bart Drinkard, Li Rebekah Feng, Luigi Ferrucci, Scott A. Gabel, Angelique Gavin, David S. Goldstein, Shahin Hassanzadeh, Sean C. Horan, Silvina G. Horovitz, Kory R. Johnson, Anita Jones Govan, Kristine M. Knutson, Joy D. Kreskow, Mark Levin, Jonathan J. Lyons, Nicholas Madian, Nasir Malik, Andrew L. Mammen, John A. McCulloch, Patrick M. McGurrin, Joshua D. Milner, Ruin Moaddel, Geoffrey A. Mueller, Amrita Mukherjee, Sandra Muñoz-Braceras, Gina Norato, Katherine Pak

c-Met-Akt pathway-mediated enhancement of inhibitory c-Raf phosphorylation is involved in vitamin K1 and sorafenib synergy on HCC growth inhibition

Cancer Biology & Therapy (2011) - 1 Comment

pubmed: 21734462 doi: 10.4161/cbt.12.6.16053 issn: 1538-4047 issn: 1555-8576

Brian I. Carr, Ziqiu Wang, Meifang Wang, Aldo Cavallini, Rosalba D'Alessandro, Maria Grazia Refolo

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#1 Sholto David comment accepted June 2025

Across multiple figures, there are western blots that are more similar than expected. I've added the coloured rectangles to show where I mean. Identified with the help of [ImageTwin.ai](https://www.imagetwin.ai). Would the authors please check and comment?

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- **Action Space: Performance and Masterclass at the University of Salford, UK – 15th November 2018**

Paper Presentation

- **Reinventing the Archive: Creative applications of search from the past – 5th September 2018, Crosstown Traffic Conference, University of Huddersfield, UK.**

Joint paper presentation with Justin Richards.

<https://www.crosstowntraffic2018.co.uk/entry/>

Item 2: List of Performances, Masterclasses and Paper Presentations

Journal contribution posted on 2019-04-08 in University of Salford

[Simon Connor](#)

Deza Regional Science High School-X
Division of Cagayan de Oro City

Garnished concept paper presentations (GCPPs) have the potential to enhance learner success and 21st-century skills in academic research. This study investigated the effectiveness of GCPPs in a mixed-methods study with 114 Senior High School Grade 12 students taking English for Academic and Professional Purposes. The quantitative results showed that GCPPs led to higher levels of learner engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes than traditional concept paper presentations (TCPPs). The qualitative results from focus group interviews with learners and instructors revealed that GCPPs were more engaging and motivating than TCPPs and that they promoted the development of 21st-century skills such as critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication.

Keywords: academic research, critical thinking, garnished concept paper presentations, learner success, 21st-century skills

Gynecologic Cancer

Therapeutic evidence (TE) required for metastatic cervical cancer: Subsequent therapy data from EUSOCC and GOG 3021 (poster) TV 301

Abstract

Program being developed with Genentech A/S

[View abstract](#)

A phase III study of nab-paclitaxel in combination with pegylated liposomal doxorubicin (PLD) in patients with platinum-resistant ovarian cancer (OC): Phase I results

Study ID

This presentation is publication only

Hematologic Malignancies

Safety outcomes in patients with acute myeloid leukemia receiving gemtuzumab ogadonin and proceeding to

Supplementary material for the presentation: ASCO 2024 Scientific Presentation Pamphlet

Journal contribution posted on 2024-05-31 in Pfizer

[Mauricio Federico Becker](#) ▼

Distinction between the effects of parental and fetal genomes on fetal growth. Julkander et al. *Nature Genetics* 2011 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/ng.081>

Slide 10: Fasting plasma glucose and insulin secretion (FPG/INS)

The trans-ancestral genomic architecture of glycemic traits. Chen et al. *Nature C* <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-021-00852-2>

Common genetic variants highlight the role of insulin resistance and body fat in diabetes, independent of obesity. Scott et al. *Diabetes* 2014 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2337/14>

A Central Role for GPR119 in Regulation of Insulin Function in Man. Prakash-Sinha et al. 2014 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0196503>

Slide 11: FPG/INS/FAI implicating ADCY5 in fasting plasma glucose, type 2 diabetes and BMI/WH weight

New genetic loci implicated in fasting glucose homeostasis and their impact on type 2 diabetes risk. Dupuis et al. *Nature Genetics* 2009 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/ng.450>

Va birth in ADCY5 and near CCNE1 are associated with fetal growth and birth weight. Freedby et al. *Nature Genetics* 2010 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/ng.347>

Slide 15: Additional funding acknowledgements for IGC in bioRxiv

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Item 2: List of Performances, Masterclasses and Paper Presentations

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Journal contribution posted on 2019-04-08, 12:25 authored by [Simon Connor](#)

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List of Performances, Masterclasses and Paper Presentations relating to the research project; Sifting Through and Sounding Out.

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● **2019-04-08** - First online date, Posted date

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Unanchored Externally Bonded Fiber Reinforced Polymer (EBFRP) System

Figure posted on 2025-05-11 in The University of Auckland

[Junrui Zhang](#) ▾

Multi-Anchored Externally Bonded Fiber Reinforced Polymer (EBFRP) System

Figure posted on 2025-05-11 in The University of Auckland

[Junrui Zhang](#) ▾

Shallow-End Anchored EBFRP System Applied to a Hollow-Core Slab

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The experimental FRP configurations were used for a 2D calibration, as shown in Fig. 4. The FRP strips were applied to the top surface of the slab, with a width of 100 mm and a length of 150 mm. The FRP strips were applied to the top surface of the slab, with a width of 100 mm and a length of 150 mm. The FRP strips were applied to the top surface of the slab, with a width of 100 mm and a length of 150 mm.

Results

All the specimens with EBFRP strips exhibited a similar load-carrying capacity, which was 15% higher than that of the control specimen. The FRP strips were applied to the top surface of the slab, with a width of 100 mm and a length of 150 mm.

Modelling

All specimens were modeled by the same finite element model. The FRP strips were applied to the top surface of the slab, with a width of 100 mm and a length of 150 mm.

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02 RESEARCH GAPS

- Existing research was limited to short and thin FRP strips with small and shallow FRP anchors, which are often not representative of real-life construction scenarios. Also, premature debonding is an undesirable failure mode that undermines scientific performance, necessitating accurate prediction [5, 6].

01 THEORETICAL VALIDATION

The Mode II is demonstrated through its ability to replicate key behaviors, including stress, slip, and bond-slip profiles, confirming its reliability for predicting structural performance.

02 EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

The results, including those from BIC analysis, show a strong correlation between the experimental data and the model's output, confirming the effectiveness of the proposed model in capturing the key mechanics of FRP-concrete interaction. Further, the

Figure posted on 2025-05-11 in The University of Auckland

SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

A systematic literature review was conducted using the Scopus and Web of Science databases spanning the period between 1994 and 2022. Yielding two datasets of existing tests.

SYSTEM BEHAVIOUR OF FIBRE ANCHORED TESTS

The intent of the anchored test was to observe if and how the anchors, including the length of the epoxy and the spacing between the anchors, modified the failure mode of the FRP strips.

✕ openscience

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← openscience

Prof Prachi Srivastava
@prachisrivas@masto.ai

🌐 5h.*

This looks very cool.

'OpenAIRE in collaboration with Area Science Park organizes a hands-on workshop titled "Where LEGO Meets FAIR Data," designed to introduce the principles of FAIR data through a creative, interactive simulation using LEGO metaphors.'

openaire.eu/eventdetail/1468/w...

 www.openaire.eu
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Here is how PCI is elevating the standards for open and reproducible science: introducing 4 already-existing and 2 new features 📖 🙌

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Some examples

Check out these examples of researchers who have already integrated the donuts into their pages:

JAMES GRECIAN Marine Ecologist

COVER PAGE/ ABOUT/ RESEARCH/ PUBLICATIONS/

Google ResearchGate iD publons

Publication Title	Altmetric Donut Value
36. Carter MID, Boehme L, Cronin MA, Duck CD, Grecian WJ , Hastie GD, Jessopp MJ, Matthiopoulos J, McConnell BJ, Miller DL, Morris CD, Moss SEW, Thompson D, Thompson PM and Russell DJF (2022) Sympatric seals, satellite tracking and protected areas: habitat-based distribution estimates for conservation and management. <i>Frontiers in Marine Science</i> 9: 875869	42
35. de la Vega C, Buchanan P, Jeffreys RM, Hopkins J, Kershaw J, Grecian WJ , Norman L, Fried AK, Biuw M, Haug T, Smout S, Tagliabue A and Mahaffey C (2022) Multi-decadal environmental change in the Barents Sea recorded by seal teeth <i>Global Change Biology</i> 28(9): 3054-3065	63
34. Grecian, W. J. , Stenson, G. B., Biuw, M., Boehme, L., Folkow, L. P., Goulet, P. J., Jonsen, I. D., Malde, A., Norday, E. S., Rosing-Asvid, A. & Smout, S. (2022) Environmental drivers of population-level variation in the migratory and diving ontogeny of an Arctic top predator <i>Royal Society Open Science</i> 9: 211042	60
33. Smout, S., Murray, K., Aerts, G., Biuw, M., Brasseur, S., Buren, A., Empacher, F., Frie, A. K., Grecian, J. , Hammill, M., Mikkelsen, B., Mosnier, A., Rosing Asvid, A., Russell, D., Skaug, H., Stenson, G., Thomas, L., ver Hoef, J., Witting, L., Zabavnikov, V., Øigård, T. A., Fernandez, R. and Wickson, F. (2021) Report of the NAMMCO-ICES Workshop on Seal Modelling (WKSEALS 2020). <i>NAMMCO Scientific Publications</i> 12.	3

Marine Biologist James Grecian has integrated donuts into the publications list on his website – [take a look](#).

Steven J. Davis University of California, Irvine | Dept. of Earth System Science

Satisfying global demand for energy, food, and goods without adding CO₂ to the atmosphere is a central challenge of the 21st century. My research aims to both better understand the problems and point the way to feasible solutions.

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Tweets by SteveDavisUCI

Article Title	Altmetric Donut Value	Altmetric Bar Chart Value
Land-use emissions embodied in trade <i>Science</i> May 6, 2022	6	466
Emissions rebound from the COVID-19 pandemic <i>Nature Climate Change</i> March 31, 2022	11	196
Cement and steel - nine steps to net-zero <i>Nature</i> March 24, 2022	9	348

Steve Davis, Associate Professor of Earth System Science at the University of California has added the Altmetric donuts and bar badges to his webpage – [check](#)

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- Increase societal impact, help solve problems

DISCUSSION

What was your experience with Open Science and Open Innovation tools so far?

What went OK?

What could have been better?

Artificial Intelligence in Open Science

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<https://www.openaire.eu/blogs/ai-with-and-for-open-science>

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AI FOR AND WITH
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Open Science and AI

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<https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/exploring-opportunities-and-challenges-intersection-open-science-and-artificial-intelligence>

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- **reproducibility crisis** (in which other researchers cannot replicate experiments conducted using AI tools)
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- **data challenges** (while high quality data is foundational to AI applications, researchers consistently face challenges related to its volume, heterogeneity and potential for bias)

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Artificial Intelligence and Open Science EIFL Training Programme Outline for Librarians and Open Science Trainers

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Framework for Using Generative AI in Research

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GenAI for Research Infrastructure

GenAI for Data Collection and Generation

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- C. Research Translation Stage
- D. Research Funding & Funding Agreement Compliance Stage

Perspectives and Cultural Norms

Using Generative AI in Research

UNESCO decision tree on when it's viable to use Chat GPT

Figure 1: When is it safe to use ChatGPT?⁵

Using Generative AI in Research

UNESCO decision tree
on when it's viable to
use Chat GPT

Current and Potential Value of LLMs for Academic Research

RESPONSIBLE USE OF GENERATIVE AI IN RESEARCH

- ✓ Remain ultimately responsible for scientific output.
- ✓ Use generative AI transparently.
- ✓ Pay particular attention to issues related to privacy, confidentiality and intellectual property rights when sharing sensitive or protected information with AI tools.
- ✓ When using generative AI, respect applicable national, EU and international legislation, as in their regular research activities.
- ✓ Continuously learn how to use generative AI tools properly to maximise their benefits, including by undertaking training.
- ✓ Refrain from using generative AI tools substantially in sensitive activities that could impact other researchers or organisations (for example peer review, evaluation of research proposals, etc).

March 2024 https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/news/all-research-and-innovation-news/guidelines-responsible-use-generative-ai-research-developed-european-research-area-forum-2024-03-20_en

Using Generative AI in Research

Using Artificial Intelligence (AI) Tools in Research, Guidance on using AI tools in research

University of Iowa

<https://its.uiowa.edu/services/protecting-sensitive-data/using-artificial-intelligence-ai-tools-research#want-to-see-an-ai-tool-in-action>

- **Generating Research Ideas** - AI tools can help generate ideas by providing you with a list of related keywords or phrases that you can use to narrow down your research focus.
- **Finding Relevant Information** - AI tools can generate a list of articles, papers, and other sources that might be relevant to your research.
- **Generating Titles and Summaries** - AI tools can help generate titles or short summaries for your research writing.
- **Generating Content** - AI tools can generate several paragraphs about your research topic that you can use as inspiration for your own content.
- **what limitations should I be aware of when using AI tools?**
- **Bias and Discrimination:** AI tools can inherit biases. This bias can perpetuate stereotypes and discrimination in research outcomes. It is important to validate content using reliable resources.
- **Plagiarism:** Content generated from AI often paraphrases from other sources. This might raise concerns regarding plagiarism and intellectual property rights. Many Federal agencies have tools to detect AI-generated content. Be aware of these tools and their potential impact on your research and research writings.
- **Data Privacy and Legal Issues:** The UI prohibits the use of AI tools with University/Internal, Restricted, and Critical data types. Once the data is placed into AI tools, the data becomes available to the public and open source. This would likely have legal consequences should a data breach occur. Please refer to the [IT Security and Policy Office's AI guidance](#).
- **Data Misinformation:** AI tools can generate data that is misinformed or inaccurate. It is extremely important to cross-reference generated content with reliable sources.

AI & plagiarism

AI: Creates content by analyzing and synthesizing vast amounts of data, but it may unintentionally replicate existing material.

Plagiarism: Involves intentionally or unintentionally copying someone else's work without proper credit.

Check paper or essay against other author work

Choose a reliable tool

Check in 2-3 tools

Check the original data

Check images against AI image creation

AI & plagiarism

Detecting Research Misconduct in the Age of Artificial Intelligence

In 2023, academic journals [retracted](#) nearly **14,000** papers, up from around **2,000** a decade before. Plagiarism and concerns about data authenticity accounted for most of the cases, with many papers showing clear "fingerprints" of research misconduct.

Detection or Deception: The Double-Edged Sword of AI in Research Misconduct – The Scientist, December 2024

<https://www.the-scientist.com/detection-or-deception-the-double-edged-sword-of-ai-in-research-misconduct-72354>

AI in Turnitin

The screenshot shows the Turnitin Feedback Studio interface. At the top, the user is identified as Silviu Vert, and the document is titled 'IEEE Open Cipri Radu'. The document content includes an 'INDEX TERMS' section with terms like 'Image sharpening', 'dilated filters', and 'Extended filters', and an 'INTRODUCTION' section discussing digital imaging and image enhancement techniques. A notification pop-up in the center reads: 'New messaging for scores under 20%. As a result of customer feedback and additional testing, we learned that AI writing detection results under 20% have a higher incidence of false positives. In order to reduce the likelihood of misinterpretation, we have changed the AI indicator to contain an asterisk for percentages less than 20 to call attention to the fact that the score is less reliable. It is essential to understand the limitations of AI detection before making decisions about a student's work. We encourage you to learn more about Turnitin's AI detection capabilities before using the tool.' The AI detection score for the document is shown as 4%.

This screenshot shows a different view of the Turnitin Feedback Studio interface, displaying a document from 'www.researchgate.net'. The document content includes an 'INTRODUCTION' section discussing image enhancement techniques and their applications. The AI detection score for this document is shown as 4%. The interface also displays the 'IEEE Access' logo and the author information: 'Author et al.: Preparation of Papers for IEEE TRANSACTIONS and JOURNALS'. The page number is 1 of 17, and the word count is 14519.

AI in Turnitin

The pervasive presence of social media platforms in contemporary society has fundamentally altered the dynamics of human interaction and communication. From the proliferation of Facebook to the rise of Instagram influencers, social media has become an integral aspect of daily life for billions worldwide. However, amid the convenience and connectivity afforded by these platforms lies a nuanced relationship with mental health that warrants deeper exploration. This essay embarks on a comprehensive journey to dissect the multifaceted impact of social media on mental well-being, delving into its intricate layers and divergent effects.

Despite the myriad challenges posed by social media, it is essential to acknowledge its potential for positive impact on mental health when utilized mindfully. Online support groups and communities offer invaluable resources and solidarity for individuals facing mental health challenges, providing a sense of belonging and understanding in times of need. Additionally, social media platforms serve as powerful tools for raising awareness about mental health issues and reducing stigma through advocacy efforts and storytelling.

To mitigate the negative effects of social media on mental health, individuals can adopt proactive strategies to cultivate a healthy relationship with these platforms. Setting boundaries around social media usage, such as limiting screen time and prioritizing offline interactions, can help restore

56% detected as AI ⓘ

The percentage indicates the combined amount of likely AI-generated text as well as likely AI-generated text that was also likely AI-paraphrased.

Submission Breakdown

- 1 AI-generated only 24%
Likely AI-generated text from a large-language model.
- 2 AI-generated text that was AI-paraphrased 32%
Likely AI-generated text that was likely revised using an AI-paraphrase tool or word spinner.

FAQs

[View FAQs](#)

Resources

[Explore](#)

Guides

[View guides](#)

Hide Disclaimer

Our AI writing assessment is designed to help educators identify text that might be prepared by a generative AI tool. Our AI writing assessment may not always be accurate (it may misidentify writing that is likely AI generated as AI generated and AI paraphrased or likely AI generated and AI paraphrased writing as only AI generated) so it should not be used as the sole basis for adverse actions against a student. It takes further scrutiny and human judgment in conjunction with an organization's application of its specific academic policies to determine whether any academic misconduct has occurred.

Plagiarism and AI tools

- Tunitin – AI
- AI Content Detector <https://writer.com/ai-content-detector/>
- ZeroGPT <https://www.zerogpt.com/>
- Originality AI <https://originality.ai/>
- Proofig AI that can detect AI-generated images
<https://www.proofig.com/>

AI Citation

Transparency about the use of GenAI in scientific publications, project applications and doctoral theses

Reference styles

APA

Chicago

IEEE

MLA

AI Citation

APA style

APA views quotes from a ChatGPT chat session as akin to sharing an algorithm's output, and recommend crediting the author of the algorithm with a reference list entry and the corresponding in-text citation.

In-text citations

- **In-text citation rule:** (Algorithm author, year)
- **Parenthetical citation:** (OpenAI, 2023)
- **Narrative citation:** OpenAI (2023)

In-text citation example (from [APA style blog](#)): When prompted with “Is the left brain right brain divide real or a metaphor?” the ChatGPT-generated text indicated that although the two brain hemispheres are somewhat specialized, “the notation that people can be characterized as ‘left-brained’ or ‘right-brained’ is considered to be an oversimplification and a popular myth” (OpenAI, 2023).

Reference list

- OpenAI. (2023). *ChatGPT* (March 14 version) [Large language model]. <https://chat.openai.com/chat>

AI Citation

Chicago Style with footnotes

¹ Text generated by ChatGPT, OpenAI, March 7, 2023, <https://chat.openai.com/>

If the prompt hasn't been included in the text, it can be included in the note:

¹ ChatGPT, response to "Explain how to make pizza dough from common household ingredients," OpenAI, March 7, 2023, <https://chat.openai.com/>

Chicago Author-Date

Any information not included in the text is placed in the parenthetical reference.

Example:

- (ChatGPT, March 7, 2023)

AI Citation

IEEE

According to the Guidelines for Artificial Intelligence (AI)-Generated Text (based on [IEEE Author Center Submission Guidelines](#)),

The use of content generated by artificial intelligence (AI) (including but not limited to text, figures, images, and code) shall be disclosed in an acknowledgments section. The AI system used shall be identified, and specific sections of the document that use AI-generated content shall be identified and accompanied by a brief explanation regarding the level at which the AI system was used to generate the content. The use of AI systems for editing and grammar enhancement should be disclosed as noted above.

Example

ChatGPT. (GPT-4). OpenAI. Accessed: Sep. 26, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://chat.openai.com/chat>

<https://open.ieee.org/author-guidelines-for-artificial-intelligence-ai-generated-text/>

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IEEE Education VicePresident for Conferences

IEEE Romania Education Chair,

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IEEE Computer Society, TCLT Open Chair

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EUA Digital Transformation Steering committee

EDEN Fellow 2011, Senior Fellow 2021

EDEN Vice-president (2017-2021)

Elearning.upt.ro

cv.upt.ro

Unicampus.ro

CUESTIONARIO DE DIANA ANDONE

1 Which of the following practices is NOT typically considered part of Open Science?

- A) Using open peer review.
- B) Sharing preprints before formal publication.
- C) Publishing only in closed-access journals.**

2 ¿In the context of EU regulations and Open Science, what does “green” open access refer to?

- A) Depositing a version of the paper in an open repository, often after an embargo.**
- B) Publishing only environmentally themed research.
- C) Publishing in fully open access journals funded by author fees.

3 When using Generative AI in academic research, which practice ensures responsible and transparent use?

- A) Avoiding any mention of AI tools in research papers.
- B) Replacing all peer-reviewed references with AI outputs.
- C) Citing AI tools and outputs properly in line with academic standards.**

Interoperable open-source tools to enable hybridisation, utilisation, and monetisation of storage flexibility

Financiado por
la Unión Europea

“If you want to go fast, go alone. If you want to go far, go together.”

African proverb.

Interoperable open-source tools

InterSTORE Horizon Europe Project

InterSTORE is an EU-funded project that aims to deploy and demonstrate a set of interoperable Open-Source tools to integrate Distributed Energy Storage (DES) and Distributed Energy Resources (DER), to enable the hybridization, utilisation and monetisation of storage flexibility, within a real-life environment. Demonstrate 7 high impact use cases in 4 real life living labs. Use beyond the state-of-the-art methods to enable hybridization, utilisation and monetisation of storage flexibility, while also ensuring data space standardization.

Based on the contents provided

Objectives

- **Understand the importance and value of open-source interoperable tools** for enabling the integration and operation of Distributed Energy Resources (DERs).
- **Appreciate the role of data sovereignty, integrity, and monetization mechanisms** in secure data exchange within digital energy ecosystems.
- **Recognize how hybrid energy storage systems can be optimized** using open-source methodologies to support modern energy systems and smart grid applications.

Main developments

Three Open-source tools:

IEEE2030.5 upgrade - (utilization)

Client/server Library for NATS Coms. The LPC converter from MODBUS and MQTT to an IEEE2030.5 format using JSON and XML. Testing procedures NATS communication system delivers fast and many-to-many communication, unleashing several use cases such as coordination between edge/EMS

Data Space connector UI - (monetization)

The data space connector is a platform that allows data to be shared peer to peer ensuring data privacy, sovereignty, data integrity and allowing monetization. Based on the initial OneNet connector, 3 new features were developed supporting the use cases and several valorization cases

Optimal battery storage (hybridization) tool

A 3 step script/methodology for hybridization (sizing) of energy storage units and also providing guidelines for technology selection. Hybrid storage systems are an example of distributed energy resources explored in InterSTORE.

Project pillars

This project has received funding from the European Commission Horizon Europe Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101096511

Use Cases and TOOLS

TOOL 1: Interoperable client/server for Distributed Energy Storage

This project has received funding from the European Commission Horizon Europe Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101096511

TOOL 2: Legacy systems protocol converter

TOOL 2: Legacy systems protocol converter

```
{
  "datetime": "28-08-2023 12:00:35",
  "status": "active",
  "start": "28-08-2023",
  "duration": 900
}
```


transformations:

- name: JSON IncomingEvent to XML IEEE2030.5 Event
- description: Example showing transformation of messages from JSON to XML

connections:

```
incoming-connection:
  - MQTT-connection
incoming-topic: topic1
incoming-format: JSON
outgoing-connection:
  - NATS-connection
outgoing-topic: event/myevent
outgoing-format: XML
```

to-outgoing:

```
'<Event>
  <creationTime>${timestamp}</creationTime>
  <EventStatus>
    <currentStatus>
      <lpc:mapping>
        <path type="integer">/status</path>
        <values>["scheduled", "active", "cancelled", "cancelled_with_r", "superseded"]</values>
      </lpc:mapping>
    </currentStatus>
    <dateTime>
```

```
<Event>
  <creationTime>1702909917932</creationTime>
  <EventStatus>
    <currentStatus>1</currentStatus>
    <dateTime>1693216835000</dateTime>
    <potentiallySuperseded>>false</potentiallySuperseded>
  </EventStatus>
  <interval>
    <duration>900</duration>
    <start>1693216835000</start>
  </interval>
</Event>
```


Support for Configuration files setup

The LPC Generator supports the file configuration for the LPC. It is designed to provide more straightforward and simplified process of configuring parameters to run the LPC. It is accessible [here](#):

TOOL 3: TESTING PROCEDURE SOFTWARE TOOL

- ▶ Testing Procedures Based on Sunspec's "Common Smart Inverter Profile (CSIP) Conformance Test Procedures"
- ▶ Automated Testing
- ▶ A Middleware facilitates the communication from client to server

TOOL 3: Overview of Testing Schematic

- The Client Test Library comprises Standard test cases
- Middleware is the part doing the communication using NATS
- Middleware initiates the test by accessing client test library
- Server Library is made of IEEE 2030.5 Resources
- Response of the test is transported through Middleware to client test library

TOOL 3: Deployment and Use Case of Test Software

- For local machines and raspberry pi, docker compose will be used
- The software can also be deployed in Kubernetes
- Development based on Java
- The test software will test the partners IEEE 2030.5 Supported Devices

Summary

- Tested in 4 pilot sites
- Integrated in different platforms and devices
- Used for monitoring and control, bidirectionality
- Communication < 100ms
- Suitable for fast grid service provision

Interoperable Data Spaces

Developments in InterSTORE

key elements in data management in support of a data economy need to be fulfilled:

- **Data models / Semantics:** Defining an appropriate data model beyond a single sector is a key ingredient for interoperability.
- **Context Information:** Defining the context is a key ingredient for bringing the gap between different verticals.
- **Data Sovereignty:** The ability of a data owner to define what a third party is allowed to do with her/his data.
- **Open API:** Closed solutions will not create a real open and competitive market. Open APIs offer the perfect bridge between private infrastructure spaces.

The Interoperable Data Space Framework consists of two main components: the Data Space Middleware (OneNet) and the Energy Data Space Connector (3 new developments).

It leverages on the IDS Reference Architectural Model as well on the FIWARE NGSI Standardized interfaces for implementing a seamless end-to-end data exchange, ensuring to data owner a full control and management over its own data.

High-level architecture of the Interoperable Data Space

Three new developments for the connector

i) User Interface; ii) blockchain registry; iii) push mechanism

Interoperable Data Spaces Framework

New UI for Interstore Connector

Energy Data Space Connector

Sign in to start your session

Remember Me

EnergyDataSpace Connector

EngProvider

Search

- Dashboard
- Services
- Cross platform services
- My offered services
- Requests
- My subscriptions
- Data exchange
- Connector settings

Home

Cross platform services

- + 00 - Generic- User defined service
- + 08 - Pre-Qualification
- + 03 - Forecasts
- + 02 - Measurements and Monitoring
- + 04 - Reports and Invoices
- + 05 - Market
- + 06 - Grid Models
- + 07 - Simulation Results
- + 09 - Service Activation
- + 10 - Resource Control

#	Category	Service	Service Description	BO code	BO Name	Profile Format
	<input type="text" value="Filter"/>	<input type="text" value="Filter"/>	<input type="text" value="Filter"/>	<input type="text" value="Filter"/>	<input type="text" value="Filter"/>	<input type="text" value="Filter"/>
1	05	OneNet_05MRKT_0012_new	This service allows for the sharing Merit Order List (MOL) for selected bids, Market Time Units.	122	Merit Order List for mFRR (balancing services)	xml
2	00	00	Any description should be add be the potential service provider	00	Generic	csv
3	00	00	Any description should be add be the potential service provider	EN202	District Heating Grid Aggregated Flexibility for Balancing Service	json
4	03	OneNet_03FORC_0001	Exchange forecast data for environmental parameters (weather), load, generation, or storage (either combined or one forecast per type)	50	Forecast data (load, generation, FSP)	
5	02	OneNet_02MEMO_0004	Exchange of grid state information	104	State Estimation Data	
6	02	OneNet_02MEMO_0004	Exchange of grid state information	44	Forecast data (load, generation, FSP)	
7	10	OneNet_10RECO_0003	Regulation of voltage and/or frequency; Exchange of instructions/control scheme for regulation of a system parameter	106	system parameter control schema/ instructions	
8	10	OneNet_10RECO_0002	Management of Assets; Exchange of execution orders to achieve a specific objective (e.g. islanding operation, balancing, energy efficiency enablement, flexibility services) Automated order, automated order end Order registration, order reception registration Limitation order, limitation order end Order reception log, end or order reception log, order execution log, end of order execution log	37	Execution order	
9	10	OneNet_10RECO_0001	Activation of Assets (RES, storage, flexibility resources, DSO assets): Exchange of activation signals for a specific asset or group of assets	90	(Flexibility) Resources	
10	10	OneNet_10RECO_0001	Activation of Assets (RES, storage, flexibility resources, DSO assets): Exchange of activation signals for a specific asset or group of assets	89	(Flexibility) Resources	

ENGINEERING

THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION COMPANY

2024

Interoperable Data Spaces Framework

New Blockchain Service

Interoperable Data Spaces Framework

New Blockchain Service

- Once a transaction occurs, it is registered in the timeline, in the same way when it does not use any blockchain option.
- The timeline provides, who consumed and who provided data, at what time, the name of the file, the category and the size.
- Once the transaction is done, it is published in the polygon public network and can be consulted by anyone (using for example the Amoy explorer)

Interoperable Data Spaces Framework

The Advantages of the Push Mechanism

- **External Service Integration:** Facilitates seamless integration with third-party systems and external services, enabling automated responses and real-time actions.
- (Near) **Real-Time Data Delivery:** Ensures that data is transmitted immediately upon creation, which is crucial for time-sensitive operations like demand-response programs or grid balancing.
- **Reduced Latency:** Minimizes the time between data generation and delivery, enhancing responsiveness and supporting real-time analytics.
- **Efficient Resource Utilization:** Reduces the computational load and network traffic for data consumers by eliminating frequent polling requests.
- **Support for Event-Driven Use Cases:** Ideal for scenarios that require immediate action based on specific events, such as equipment failures, energy demand spikes, or renewable energy fluctuations.
- **Proactive Stakeholder Actions:** Empowers stakeholders to make swift, data-driven decisions by receiving timely alerts and notifications, enabling preventive maintenance, and optimizing energy distribution strategies.

Interoperable Data Spaces Framework

New Scenario: Service Subscribe and Push data

1. The Service Provider creates a new service, implements a Rest Web Service, and specifies the URL of the service to be called (in the Push Service creation GUI)
2. A Data provider subscribe to the service, and after request has been accepted from service provider, can push data using the connector in a classic way.
3. During loading, the configured web service is called synchronously with the file and metadata, making data immediately available to the Service Provider.
4. Finally, a response confirms success or returns an error code/message.

Summary

- 3 new features developed for the DS connector
- Integration with the IEEE2030.5 + NATS
- 4 valorization cases created
- Tested in 4 demo sites
- > 9 services created with thousands of files exchanges during the project

Hybridization model

What is a hybrid energy storage system?

“(…) an operational combination of storage technologies with different characteristics to downsize the overall system, decrease the costs or to increase the lifetime, system efficiency or other performance measures.”

Time Series Clustering- Recurring patterns

- Time Series Clustering for Recurring Pattern identification or cycles.
- The Dynamic Time warping algorithm was used to take into account time shifts.
- This approach can be replicated with similar data frames from any load profile.

Time Series Clustering- Recurring patterns

- 1) Data Collection:** A year load data from the PT demo site was used (01/01/2022 to 01/01/2023), 15 min. time step.
- 2) Data Preprocessing:** Cleaning data, handling missing values, outliers.
- 3) Dynamic Time Warping (DTW):** This technique measures the similarity between two-time series that may vary over time.
- 4) Clustering analysis:** Cluster analysis that constructs a hierarchy of clusters by successively merging or splitting groups of data.

Time Series Clustering- Recurring patterns

5) Load Profile Analysis:

- With the recurring pattern, a box plot is generated.
- Maximum values, consistency and means are evaluated to assess the Max_Power to be considered

Total Energy Demanded by the Load: 1698.0 kWh

- Considers the median from the box plot data, to be the load diagram for the next stage. The energy needs can hence be determined.
- These parameters will be used as inputs for the subsequent section of the model.

Optimization – Maximize Energy supplied by the HESS

- **Load profile** - It comes from the clustering exercise with the recurring pattern

load = [32.0, 31.0, 32.0, 31.0, 31.0, 31.0, 38.5, 57.0, 76.0, 121.5, 171.0, 155.0, 117.5, 92.0, 90.0, 108.0, 96.5, 88.0, 78.0, 67.0, 48.0, 39.0, 34.0, 33.0]

- **Set original battery size**

1) Max_Power is the maximum of the box plots (plus a k factor to account for avoiding 100% load capacity, considered here to be 8%)

-> Max_Power=250 kW

2) Max_Energy is the point where the % of energy supplied from the battery no longer improves (marginal gain starts decreasing) when the energy capacity increases.

-> Max_energy = 250 kWh -> Corresponds to a **C-Rate 1**

Battery Daily Dispatch

Hour (h)	Power Input kW (P_{in})	Power Output kW (P_{out})	SOC
0	0.0	0.0	0.0
1	250.0	0.0	250.0
2	0.0	32.0	218.0
3	0.0	31.0	187.0
4	0.0	31.0	156.0
5	0.0	31.0	125.0
6	125.0	0.0	250.0
7	0.0	57.0	193.0
8	0.0	76.0	117.0
9	0.0	117.0	0.0
10	250.0	0.0	250.0
11	0.0	155.0	95.0
12	0.0	95.0	0.0
13	198.0	0.0	198.0
14	0.0	90.0	108.0
15	0.0	108.0	0.0
16	233.0	0.0	233.0
17	0.0	88.0	145.0
18	0.0	78.0	67.0
19	0.0	67.0	0.0
20	106.0	0.0	106.0
21	0.0	39.0	67.0
22	0.0	34.0	33.0
23	0.0	33.0	0.0

The Optimization Formulation

- **Objective function (different objectives can be defined)**

$$\max \sum_{t \in T} E_{In}[t] \Delta t$$

- **Constraints**

$$SOC_t = E_{in}(t) - E_{out}(t) \quad , \quad t=0 \quad (3)$$

$$SOC_t = SOC_{t-1} + E_{in}(t) - E_{out}(t) \quad , \quad t > 0 \quad (4)$$

$$P_{in}(t) = E_{in}(t) \quad , \quad \forall t \in T \quad (5)$$

$$P_{out}(t) = E_{out}(t) \quad , \quad \forall t \in T \quad (6)$$

$$P_{in}(t) \leq \text{Max_energy} \quad , \quad \forall t \in T \quad (7)$$

$$P_{out}(t) \leq \text{Max_energy} \quad , \quad \forall t \in T \quad (8)$$

$$E_{in}(t) \leq \text{Max_energy} \quad , \quad \forall t \in T \quad (9)$$

$$E_{out}(t) \leq \text{Max_energy} \quad , \quad \forall t \in T \quad (10)$$

$$E_{in}(t) \leq \text{Charge_discharge}_t * \text{Max_energy} \quad , \quad \forall t \in T \quad (11)$$

$$E_{out}(t) \leq (1 - \text{charge_discharge}_t) * \text{Max_energy} \quad , \quad \forall t \in T \quad (12)$$

$$P_{out}(t) \leq \text{Load} \quad , \quad \forall t \in T \quad (13)$$

$$SOC_{t=0} = SOC_{t=23} = 0 \quad (14)$$

- Max Energy Provided by the battery Required by the load:

$$E_{Total\ Demand} = \sum_{t=0}^{23} P_{load}(t)$$

- Energy Provided by the Battery:
- % satisfied by the battery:

Optimization – Maximize Energy supplied by the HESS

The load comes from the from the 2nd stage of the model

Output:

Total Energy Provided to the Load by the battery: 1222.5 kWh

Total Energy Demanded by the Load: 1698.0 kWh

Percentage of energy supplied by the battery: 72.0 %

Daily Dispatch Output:

Optimization – Maximize Energy supplied by the HESS

- Example of the energy capacity estimation for the battery

Adjust Energy Capacity:

Run the model in a loop with different values of energy capacity and observe the Percentage of energy supplied by the battery. When the marginal gain starts decreasing, consider it to be optimal. This means that increasing one unit in energy capacity results in lower and lower gains in percentage output supplied (similar to the elbow method)

Run the model for (adjust to your case):

- min_energy = 125
- max_energy = 1700
- Step=100

Hybridization model fundamentals

- Consider the input signal in blue
- If the breaking point (Cut-off) is at 50% of the original signal, we obtain two new signals. A base signal (green) and a peak signal (red).
- Power cut-off range from 0.1% to 99.9%, resulting in a theoretical infinite nbr of two batteries combination
- Calculating the base and peak power, and energy values for each power cut off results in a set of points showing a curve (purple) beneath the original signal vector (also purple). This curve is called the hybridization curve.
- As we can see in the third image (right) an area is created which is bound by the hybridization curve and the signal vector.

Hybridization model

Step by step – From the Cut-off to the hybridization curve

- e.g: 50%

Hybridization model fundamentals

- Let the purple vector represent the point of maximum energy and maximum power required.
- In the upper image the red and green vectors represent the characteristics of two single-battery systems, the (red) is over dimensioned in power, and the (green) in energy.
- On the bottom image a two-battery system is presented, where **both batteries of the system are under dimensioned, but when working together are exactly dimensioned to the load needs.**
- The two-battery system can outperform a single-battery system because the pair joint characteristics can better match the dispatch signal necessities without being over dimensioned.

Hybridization model - Results

Two solution, one optimal the other non-optimal

- **Solution 1:**
Base Battery: 80 kW; 110 kWh
Peak Battery: 170kW; 367kWh
- **Solution 2:**
Base Battery: 200 kW; 200 kWh
Peak Battery: 50kW; 277kWh

Summary

- Technology agnostic model for hibridization
- Distinction between power based and energy based batteries
- Based on recurring pattern identification
- Supports different optimization functions
- Validated with third party min. cost optimization model

InterSTORE Open-source practices

- All developments were uploaded in to the project's github repository
- LPC and associated developments published also in Dockerhub repositior
- Cupid project - <https://github.com/orgs/cupid-project/repositories>
- All datasets for KPI calculation and public deliverables published in Zenodo
- All articles from InterSTORE were published in open-source journals or open access
- Involvement of a stakeholders group for guidance and early adoption

The image shows two screenshots related to the InterSTORE project. The top screenshot is the GitHub organization page for 'Horizont-Europe-Interstore'. It displays a grid of popular repositories including 'Data-Space-Connector-Firmware-Data-App', 'Hybrid-Storage-Sizing-Model', 'Client-Server', 'Data-Space-Connector-UI', 'Data-Space-Connector', and 'Testing-procedure-and-software-tools'. The bottom screenshot is the Zenodo repository page for 'Interoperable open-source Tools to Enable hybridisation, utilisation, and monetisation of stORage fleXibility'. It shows the repository title, description, and a list of versions, with the latest version being 'October 1, 2023 (v1.1)'. The Zenodo page also includes a 'New upload' button and a 'Records' section.

Outcome

- All tools have been or are now being used or proposed in other projects to be built upon
- The FAIR approach followed in European Projects is consonant with open source-practices
- Open-source tools are able to get much depth of development due to community effort
- Promotes collaboration between research partners while enabling integration in other contexts
- Sustainability and Independence of developments

Obrigado

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CUESTIONARIO DE ALEXANDER LUCAS

1 What is the main advantage of using interoperable open-source tools like those developed in the InterSTORE project for integrating distributed energy resources (DERs) and storage systems?

- A) They completely eliminate the need for communication standards like IEEE 2030.5.
- B) They guarantee that all energy storage systems will automatically become cost-free.
- C) They allow seamless integration, hybridization, and monetization across different systems while ensuring collaboration and openness.**

2 What is a hybrid energy storage system (HESS)?

- A) It's a storage system that uses at least two fuels to run.
- B) A HESS is battery with lower power and energy density capable providing specific services maximizing profit.
- C) An operational combination of storage technologies with different characteristics to downsize the overall system, decrease the costs or to increase the lifetime, system efficiency or other performance measures**

3 Why is integrating Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) into energy systems often a challenge?

- A) Because DERs always consume more energy than they generate.
- B) Because DERs are diverse, use different communication protocols, and lack interoperability, making coordination difficult.**
- C) Because DERs are already standardized worldwide and never need adaptation.

Interoperable Recommender

Enhancing Energy System Resilience with a Recommendation System for Voluntary Demand Response

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Content

- InterConnect project
- Motivation & Objectives
- Common European Reference Framework
- Interoperable Recommender
 - Objectives
 - Methodology
 - Key results
 - Ecosystem
- Open practices and outcomes
- Conclusions

InterConnect project

- **H2020 Large Scale Pilot (2019-2024):** 50+ European entities to develop and demonstrate advanced solutions for connecting and converging digital homes and buildings with the electricity sector.
- Cross-domain semantic interoperability based on SAREF
- Validation in 7 large-scale test-sites (PT, BE, DE, NL, IT, EL and FR)

Motivation & Objectives

Challenges and Roadmap for Energy Resilience in Europe

- Climate change, geopolitical risks, decarbonization → increased reliance on **varying renewable energy**
- Greater **flexibility in energy consumption** to help prevent periods of excess demand or energy generation
- Aligned with the EU's action plan goals by promoting **smarter energy use**

CERF-Compliant Energy Applications

- InterConnect to support a new use case: Energy applications aligned with the Common European Reference Framework
- Use flexibility from the demand side alongside “grid signals” to engage end-users to help **improving system resilience**
- Implement a technically and scientifically credible strategy for **end-user participation**

What was the role and impact of open-source practices?

Common European Reference Framework

Interoperable Recommender

Objectives

- Methodology to assess periods of **expected system vulnerability** in Europe's energy infrastructure
- Promote **country-level actions** (increase/decrease consumption) during those periods to enhance resilience
- **Data-driven** methodology to assess vulnerability and compute actions with **publicly available data**,
- Considering the status of each country and its interconnections
- Share with interested parties through the EnergyAPP

Interoperable Recommender

Methodology

- System vulnerability
 - RES generation variability and forecast uncertainty
 - Increasing challenges of day-ahead load forecasting
- Types of risk
 - Risk of energy scarcity or renewable energy curtailment
 - Unexpected problems and unavailability of reserve capacity
- Risk mitigation
 - Calculate the system margin per country considering load and RES forecast uncertainty
 - Extract risk attributes from the system margin to assess the impact of a potential reserve level
 - Country-level actions to mitigate this risk and enhance resilience for each country and interconnections

Interoperable Recommender

Methodology

- Data Acquisition
 - Publicly accessible from [entso-e](https://entso-e.eu) Transparency Platform
- Forecasting
 - Probabilistic Forecasts (Quantiles) of RES and Load
- Risk Assessment*
 - Calculate system margin and develop risk-reserve curves
 - Calculate reliability indexes (**LOLP**, **PCRE**)
 - Find operating reserve requirements (**R**, based on TSO threshold)
 - Calculate deterministic rule for reserve (**DRR**)
- Risk Coordination
 - Assess if country's interconnection could help mitigate risk
- Final recommendation
 - $R \leq DRR$ ☐ Healthy | $R > DRR$ ☐ At Risk

*M.A. Matos, R.J. Bessa, "Setting the operating reserve using probabilistic wind power forecasts" IEEE Transactions on Power Systems, vol. 26(2), pp.594-603, May 2011.

Interoperable Recommender

Methodology

Interoperable Recommender

Key results

- Service operational during multiple months in **12 countries**
- 400+ consumers** involved in testing
- Preliminary results (PT) show **consumer response**:
 - 4% consumption decrease during *Decrease* recommendations when analyzed against *comparable days*
 - 81.6% of collected feedback showed commitment to adopt recommendations (4 to 5 stars)

Interoperable Recommender

Ecosystem

Open practices and outcomes

- Reliance on **public data** acquisition
- **Open-access** journal publication <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2024.111430>
- **Open-source** code repositories
 - Interoperable Recommender <https://github.com/INESCTEC/interoperable-recommender-iso>
 - EnergyApp <https://github.com/INESCTEC/energy-app-backend>
 - Generic Adapter <https://github.com/INESCTEC/generic-adapter>
 - (...)
- **Public deliverables** from InterConnect

ARTICLE · Volume 27, Issue 12, 111430, December 20, 2024 · Open Access

Enhancing the European power system resilience with a recommendation system for voluntary demand response

Carlos A.M. Silva ^{1,2,9} · Ricardo J. Bessa ¹ · José R. Andrade ¹ · Fábio A. Coelho ³ · Rafael B. Costa ³ · Carlos Damas Silva ⁴ · George Vlachodimitropoulos ^{5,6} · Donatos Stavropoulos ⁷ · Spiros Chadoulos ⁸ · David E. Rua ¹ Show less

Conclusions

- It was possible to develop a scientifically sound methodology to send recommendations based solely on open data
- Consumers were engaged and responded to the available recommendations
- Specialized recommendations enable avoiding conflicting objectives at the DSO level
- Open-source practices were implemented from the development to the reporting and publication phases

- Instantiate in possible future projects as the backbone to provide grid signals
- Future developments for methodology improvement, internally or via open-source community contributions
- Additional public data sources for redundancy and availability

Thank you!

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CUESTIONARIO DE CARLOS SILVA

1 What is the primary objective of the Interoperable Recommender (IR) system?

- A) To provide real-time pricing signals for electricity consumers based on market fluctuations
- B) To automate the control of household appliances to maximize energy savings without consumer input
- C) To deliver actionable recommendations to consumers for increasing or decreasing energy consumption to enhance the resilience of the European power system**

2 How does the Interoperable Recommender (IR) system calculate country-level risk for energy consumption?

- A) By relying solely on manual input from local grid operators to assess risk
- B) By combining probabilistic forecasts of renewable energy generation and load, then calculating the system margin and reserve requirements to determine risk.**
- C) By using only historical weather data to predict renewable energy generation

3 Which of the following is a key feature of the Interoperable Recommender (IR) system's methodology?

- A) It uses proprietary data from private energy companies to generate recommendations
- B) It leverages semantic interoperability to enable seamless integration with third-party services and applications**
- C) It focuses exclusively on economic incentives to encourage demand response from consumers

Predico

Collaborative Analytics

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On collaborative analytics ...

Motivation

An untapped potential?

- **Geographically distributed** (siloes) data
- Lack of **economic signals** to incentivize sharing (or collaborating with) data
- The **value** of data is **unclear** to data owners and competitors
- Forecasting often limited to **costly in-house models** (with bias risks), or **dependence on a few external suppliers**, reducing transparency and flexibility.

The opportunity

- Create a **collaborative ecosystem** where **data producers** and **forecasters** can interact
- **Monetize participation** through incentive mechanisms based on the value of the shared data
- Unlock value through a shared data pool - enabling innovative use cases like:
 - **data barter**: exchange data by data
 - **collaborative forecasting**: combine different forecast sources to improve resilience and accuracy

On energy timeseries forecasting ...

Collaborative forecasting – from research to proof-of-concept

*Internal Research
+ Seed Project*

2020-2023

*EU Projects
(First demos)*

2022-2025

*Industrial Client
(Proof of Concept)*

2024-2025

<https://predico-elia.inesctec.pt/>

On energy timeseries forecasting ...

What are companies currently doing?

Create your own internal models

Advantages

- **Customized to business** needs
- Full **control** over data and assumptions
- Proprietary insights
- Data privacy

Disadvantages

- **High** R&D and maintenance **costs**
- Requires continuous data management
- Potential **internal biases**

Purchase forecasts from suppliers

Advantages

- Specialized expertise
- Cost-effective, lower upfront investment
- Operational **simplicity**
- Tested with broader market data

Disadvantages

- Limited control over forecast process
- Dependency on **supplier reliability**
- Generic, potentially less tailored insights
- Data confidentiality risks

Predico – Collaborative Forecasting

Predico – Collaborative Forecasting

Market Session : Step-by-step

Predico – Collaborative Forecasting

Modules Breakdown

Outlier Detection

Detect abnormal forecast submissions (e.g., using DTW)

Forecasting

Regression models (LASSO Regression, Quantile Regression, Gradient Boosting, etc.)
Statistical approaches (arithmetic mean, weighted averages)

Evaluation & Payment
Processing

Calculate forecasting skill scores & distribute market maker prizes per forecasters based on predefined rules

Ongoing proof-of-concept @ Elia (Belgium TSO)

Relevant dates

**Local
Proof-of-concept**

June – October 2024

**Offshore Wind
DA Forecasting Pilot**

November 2024
- December 2025

**Country Solar
DA Forecasting Pilot**

April - December 2025

Source: <https://predico-elia.inesctec.pt/dashboard>

More info? <https://innovation.eliagroup.eu/en/projects/predico-collaborative-forecasting-platform>

Ongoing proof-of-concept @ Elia (Belgium TSO)

Target Variables – Measurement Retrieved from Elia's Open Data Portal

Peak: 7526 MW
Strong summer peaks
Seasonal

Solar

Peak: 2240 MW
Strong Wind Ramps

Wind

Ongoing proof-of-concept @ Elia (Belgium TSO)

Relevant numbers

Ongoing proof-of-concept @ Elia (Belgium TSO)

Collaborative Forecasting Challenges

Forecasting Problems

- Abnormal forecasts
(wrong scale, incorrect quantile, model issue, etc.)
- Over/Underestimation
- Submission errors (fail to submit)

Inconsistent Performance

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun
1st	A	F	H	D	G	J
2nd	B	B	C	J	K	D
3rd	C	D	A	I	C	A
4th	D	G	I	G	H	K
5th	E	A	D	A	L	G

Ongoing proof-of-concept @ Elia (Belgium TSO)

Backtesting – Real data (Jan 1st to Mar 31st) - Offshore wind | Day Ahead Forecasting

Good forecasters can fail suddenly; ML models update their trust slowly

Weighted avg. approaches offer greater robustness

(Deterministic forecasts: using just forecasters Q50 as input or Q10, Q50, Q90)

Ongoing proof-of-concept @ Elia (Belgium TSO)

Operational Results: January 1st to Aug 31st, 2025 // Offshore Wind Forecasting

forecaster	type	nr_submissions	avg RMSE	avg MWI
F15	market participant	1	102.82	665.26
ensemble	-	241	185.78	674.47
F31	contracted	240	191.51	931.24
F3	contracted	241	191.75	693.12
F10	contracted	112	194.15	773.90
F24	market participant	240	194.46	795.31
F12	market participant	216	195.41	791.89
F7	market participant	192	197.26	701.39
F26	contracted	241	200.76	740.10
F16	market participant	237	201.87	759.27
F33	market participant	234	207.31	856.73
F8	market participant	123	209.80	822.01
F32	contracted	231	211.26	770.58
F30	market participant	180	211.34	762.27
F11	market participant	237	215.83	806.49
F14	market participant	73	217.15	792.41
F6	market participant	237	219.00	839.93
F22	market participant	231	219.84	819.41
F4	market participant	194	220.36	819.38
F17	market participant	144	226.09	874.74
F5	market participant	232	235.62	863.80
F1	market participant	214	238.68	1107.00
F21	market participant	162	248.31	1098.25
F29	market participant	115	250.85	1098.69
F9	market participant	234	257.47	1064.38
F27	contracted	228	259.40	898.85
F19	market participant	133	264.47	1289.26
F2	contracted	137	267.81	966.79
F18	market participant	182	275.85	1162.82
F23	market participant	211	295.11	1291.73
F13	market participant	11	296.81	1382.66
F20	market participant	148	296.93	1020.07
F34	market participant	37	323.86	1201.48
F25	market participant	168	341.59	1831.85
F28	market participant	41	559.29	3516.45

- Best forecasts supplier differs on both tracks
- Ensemble not influenced by lower quality forecasters
- Contracted forecasters (bilateral – fixed payment) not always the best

Ongoing proof-of-concept @ Elia (Belgium TSO)

Operational Results

Offshore Wind Forecasting

(no outlier detection in place)

month	best_forecaster	Ensemble improvement over		
		best	avg. of all	avg. of top 5
2025-01	F11	5.51%	9.06%	7.10%
2025-02	F26	-6.71%	14.29%	0.02%
2025-03	F24	-2.23%	20.03%	3.73%
2025-04	F3	1.81%	18.27%	8.27%
2025-05	F31	0.30%	21.42%	4.75%
2025-06	F3	-1.56%	15.85%	0.44%
2025-07	F3	-0.99%	11.98%	1.50%
2025-08	F3	-1.10%	22.02%	3.81%

	RMSE	MWI
Average score of top 5 forecasters	196.1	751.7
Ensemble improvement over top 5 avg. score	5.2%	10.3%
Ensemble improvement over best forecaster	3.0%	2.7%
Ensemble improvement over Elia provider	7.5%	8.9%

Solar Forecasting

month	best_forecaster	Ensemble improvement over		
		best	avg. of all	avg. of top 5
2025-04	F16	6.06%	24.84%	17.25%
2025-05	F14	6.03%	32.05%	26.22%
2025-06	F11	3.84%	41.57%	12.03%
2025-07	F9	3.38%	28.15%	15.53%
2025-08	F6	-6.77%	23.88%	1.89%

	RMSE	MWI
Average score of forecasters	364.7	1121.8
Ensemble improvement over top 5 avg. score	4.2%	7.0%
Ensemble improvement over best forecaster	4.7%	-1.3%
Ensemble improvement over Elia provider	6.3%	3.1%

Ongoing proof-of-concept @ Elia (Belgium TSO)

Does size matter?

Source: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/hermancarstens_over-the-past-6-months-of-testing-the-predico-activity-7341759602868314112-8J_g

Ongoing proof-of-concept @ Elia (Belgium TSO)

What if the best forecasters leave?

Ongoing proof-of-concept @ Elia (Belgium TSO)

Graphical user interface

Available for **Market Makers** and **Individual Forecasters**

(with anonymized identifiers)

Source: <https://predico-elia.inesctec.pt/dashboard>

Ongoing proof-of-concept @ Elia (Belgium TSO)

Key Takeaways

- There is a way to **improve** forecasting accuracy, profitability and discoverability
- We have built a platform for it (**currently in proof-of-concept**)
- **25+ companies** actively using our platform
- Focused on **Renewable Energy Sources** Forecasting
(but can be expanded towards more use cases)
- Redundancy makes it robust to forecast suppliers' issues

Predico – Collaborative Forecasting

Is open source!

Follow the QR code to access our GitHub repository!

Predico – Collaborative Forecasting

Want to know more?

Visit the official web portal
of Predico Elia's PoC

Interested in joining Predico to purchase forecasts
or to supply forecasts and competing for the prize pool?

Contact us!

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herman.carstens@elia.be

Thank you.

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CUESTIONARIO DE RICARDO ANDRADE

1 What is the main goal of the Predico collaborative forecasting approach?

A) To create a collaborative ecosystem where data producers and forecasters interact, improving accuracy and resilience.

B) To eliminate the need for renewable energy forecasting entirely.

C) To create a collaborative platform where forecast suppliers purchase data to enhance their forecasts

2 What is one of the modules included in the Predico collaborative forecasting platform?

A) Federated learning to compute collaborative forecasts.

B) Outlier detection to identify abnormal forecast submissions.

C) Data imputation process to fill missing data from forecast suppliers or data owners

3 What did the Elia proof-of-concept reveal about ensemble forecasting?

A) It always ranked first in every session, outperforming all individual forecasters.

B) It was heavily influenced by the lowest-quality forecasters.

C) It was consistent over time, often in the top 5, even if did not always rank first.